

Bitcoin Price Prediction Using Deep Learning Models

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Abstract

Bitcoin has become increasingly mainstream after years of ups and downs. People's attitudes towards Bitcoin have shifted from skepticism in its early years to a willingness to explore its value and potential today. In this context, gaining a deeper understanding of Bitcoin and other cryptocurrencies is highly relevant. The significant volatility in Bitcoin's price and the resulting potential for substantial profit attract people to study its price trends and strive to improve the accuracy of its price predictions. In recent years, with the rapid development of AI, more researchers have begun to explore using machine learning and deep learning to enhance the accuracy of Bitcoin price predictions. This study aims to use state-of-the-art deep learning models to forecast Bitcoin's price. Through literature review, feature analysis, data preprocessing, automated hyperparameter tuning, comparative analysis between different deep learning models, and volatility analysis, the study compared the performance of the single LSTM model, single GRU model, LSTM-GRU hybrid model and GRU-LSTM hybrid model in predicting Bitcoin prices. The research found that, under the same settings, the GRU model outperformed not only the LSTM model but also the two hybrid models, demonstrating strong performance in Bitcoin price prediction.

1. Introduction

1.1 Bitcoin price prediction is important and profitable

Bitcoin, introduced in 2008 by a pseudonymous entity known as Satoshi Nakamoto, is both a decentralized digital payment system that operates without a central authority and the native cryptocurrency mined and transacted in this network. By combining blockchain technology, cryptography and proof-of-work consensus mechanism, a robust system for electronic transactions without relying on trust was created. From then on, internet is no more just a communication channel, it is also able to transfer value. This is revolutionary for the traditional finance, as the financial institutions serving as trusted third parties are no more necessary to process electronic payments (Nakamoto, 2008). Since then, a lot of developments of decentralized finance have been ongoing, especially after the introduction of Ethereum and its smart contracts in 2015. In fact, the underlying distributed ledger technologies (DLT) and tokenomics are regarded as revolutionary in areas far beyond the financial industry (Sandner et al., 2019). Web3, based on blockchain technology, cryptocurrencies and decentralized principles, is deemed to change the whole society, as it enables people not only to read and write but also to own, fundamentally altering interactions between individuals (Dixon, 2024). From various perspectives, Bitcoin holds milestone significance for human development.

However, throughout its relatively short history, the definition and function of Bitcoin have always been controversial. In Nakamoto's initial vision, bitcoin should be a purely peer-to-peer version of electronic cash (Nakamoto, 2008). But a Bitcoin transaction to be included in a block is about 10 minutes, which is much slower than many traditional financial transaction solutions (Velde, 2013). Hence, the payment function of Bitcoin became constrained as its acceptance grew, leading to a fork in 2017 and the creation of Bitcoin Cash (BCH)¹. While Dyhrberg (2016) positioned Bitcoin between gold's store of value and the US dollar's medium of exchange, considering it to blend attributes of both commodities and currencies and to be useful for portfolio management,

¹ <https://bitcoincash.org/en>

particularly for risk-averse investors anticipating negative news, some other academic papers concluded that Bitcoin had been mainly used as a speculative investment rather than as an alternative currency and medium of exchange (Yermack 2015; Corbet et al., 2018; Baur et al., 2018 etc.). Bouoiyour & Selmi (2015) suggested Bitcoin to be more likely a short-term hedge and risky investment than a long-term promise, and estimated that it would be more likely to collapse and disappear than to become internationally recognized. On the contrary, Bitcoin is widely deemed as digital gold due to its limited supply of 21 million coins, and its impact continues to spread worldwide, as evidenced by the approval of spot Bitcoin exchange-traded products in January 2024². At the Bitcoin Conference 2024 in Nashville, presidential candidate Trump promised to create a strategic national Bitcoin reserve if he is elected³.

Despite the numerous controversies surrounding Bitcoin, it cannot be ignored as not only the most valuable cryptocurrency but also a leading asset, with an all-time high market cap surpassing \$1.4 trillion in March 2024, pushing it past silver to become the world's eighth most valuable asset⁴. Due to the impressive rise in Bitcoin's price and its high volatility, there is a growing interest among market participants in understanding the Bitcoin system as a whole, with price predictions consistently being a focal point for many scholars and practitioners.

Bitcoin has a halving cycle approximately every four years, where the block reward on the Bitcoin network is halved after around 210,000 blocks. In each halving cycle, Bitcoin has reached a new all-time high price. The first halving took place on November 28, 2012, reducing the reward from 50 BTC to 25 BTC, with a peak price of around \$1,151 in December 2013. The second halving occurred on July 9, 2016, reducing the reward to 12.5 BTC, and Bitcoin reached a high of about \$19,497 in December 2017. The third halving happened on May 11, 2020, lowering the reward to 6.25 BTC, and the price soared to approximately \$73,135 in March 2024. The fourth halving occurred on April 20, 2024, reducing the reward to 3.125 BTC, with the highest price yet to be

² <https://www.sec.gov/newsroom/speeches-statements/gensler-statement-spot-bitcoin-011023>

³ <https://www.coindesk.com/policy/2024/07/27/if-we-dont-do-it-china-will-trumps-crypto-embrace-tightens-as-he-speaks-at-bitcoin-event-in-nashville>

⁴ <https://www.coindesk.com/markets/2024/03/11/bitcoins-market-cap-jumps-to-14t-surpassing-silver>

determined⁵.

While both the always-bullish strategy and the halving cycle investment strategy have been effective, given the significant volatility of Bitcoin's price compared to most other assets, exploring shorter-term investment strategies can also be highly profitable, where accurate price prediction plays a crucial role. Technical analysis, commonly used for stocks and other risk assets, is widely applied to the trading of Bitcoin and other cryptocurrencies. With the rise of machine learning and deep learning, many investors and researchers have begun using advanced algorithms and models to enhance their prediction accuracy.

1.2 Deep learning models are promising tools

Bitcoin price prediction is challenging due to the intricate nature of the cryptocurrency market, which is influenced by a variety of factors such as technical, legal and sentimental factors. The complexity of predicting Bitcoin prices has driven many researchers to explore the various factors affecting price fluctuations, turning Bitcoin market research into a multidisciplinary field. A range of prediction methods has been developed, from traditional regression analyses to sentiment analyses utilizing news outlets and social media. This area incorporates not only economics and finance but also computer science and data science, facilitating the creation of advanced algorithmic models aimed at providing accurate and reliable price predictions. In recent years, machine learning, particularly deep learning, has become increasingly popular due to its impressive performance and significant potential.

In fact, artificial intelligence (AI) is experiencing unprecedented growth and adoption, fundamentally transforming how businesses operate and how individuals interact with technology. Since ChatGPT was launched on 30th November 2022, it has successfully ignited the AI boom. A significant amount of capital has flowed into the AI sector, and public attention has been continuously increasing. This wave of AI has successfully propelled NVIDIA to become the world's most valuable public company in June 2024⁶. No industry can ignore the power of AI, including finance and its investment sector. As

⁵ <https://btc.com/btc/halving>

⁶ <https://www.ft.com/content/1ec5523a-80ec-47ba-9f71-8765b4ae4577>

a crucial part of AI, machine learning is able to enable automated learning and self-improvement from data, without explicit programming. This capability enhances prediction and decision-making by efficiently processing large-scale data. Among machine learning techniques, deep learning advances by effectively handling complex and unstructured large-scale data through multi-layer neural networks. It automatically extracts features from raw data, reducing the need for manual feature engineering, and achieves higher accuracy and performance, enabling end-to-end learning and streamlining the process from input to output. Many algorithmic traders and researchers have already delved deeply into asset price prediction and investment decision-making using relevant techniques. On 1st July 2024, Bridgewater launched a \$2 billion fund run by machine learning⁷. Pertinent academic studies, especially those focused on Bitcoin, are presented in the literature review section.

1.3 Research objective

The objective of this study is to explore the effectiveness of deep learning models in predicting Bitcoin prices. The specific deep learning models to be explored and compared were determined based on a review of existing studies described in the following literature review section.

1.4 Research questions

- (1) What are the most effective deep learning models for Bitcoin price prediction?
- (2) How can these models be adjusted to enhance their performance?
- (3) How do these models compare with each other?

1.5 Structure of the paper

After the introduction, this paper first reviews the existing literature, including studies on the factors influencing Bitcoin prices and research on using machine learning and deep learning to predict financial products' prices, particularly Bitcoin's price. Following that is the methodology section, which covers research design, a brief introduction to the LSTM and GRU models, the architectures of the models used in this study, model optimization tools and evaluation metrics. The fourth section is data

⁷ <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2024-07-01/bridgewater-launches-2-billion-fund-powered-by-machine-learning>

collection and preprocessing, which provides a detailed description of the data used in this study, such as Bitcoin's historical prices, technical indicators, blockchain data, and macroeconomic data, and how they were obtained and processed, as well as how the features were adjusted and determined. After briefly introducing the software and hardware implementation environment for this study, the sixth section details how the deep learning models were trained, including how the optimal hyperparameter combinations were determined, how models were created, and how their performances were measured. The seventh section then presents all the results and corresponding comparative analysis between different models. Following the conclusions section, the contributions and limitations of this study, as well as potential directions for future research, are discussed.

2. Literature review

This section is mainly divided into two parts. First, it reviews the literature on the factors influencing Bitcoin prices to determine which features should be fed into the models. Second, it reviews the literature on using machine learning, particularly deep learning, to predict financial time series, with a specific focus on studies related to predicting Bitcoin prices.

2.1 Influential factors

In existing research, the factors influencing Bitcoin prices can be roughly categorized into the following three types: fundamentals and macroeconomy, market microstructure, and investors' attention and interest. Below, representative research findings for each category are presented, and the most influential parameters for bitcoin price prediction are listed.

2.1.1 Fundamentals and macroeconomy

Georgoula et al. (2015) found that in the short term, there was a negative correlation between Bitcoin prices and the exchange rate between the US dollar and the euro, and over the long term, the S&P 500 index negatively influenced Bitcoin prices, suggesting that investors would perceive stocks and Bitcoins as substitutes.

However, Ciaian et al. (2016) concluded that the global macro-financial development,

represented by the oil price, USD-EUR exchange rate and Dow Jones Index, only impacted Bitcoin price in the short run.

Vassiliadis et al. (2017) found that the bitcoin price was strongly correlated with major stock market indices, including NASDAQ, DAX, and S&P 500, without lag, while it was also strongly correlated with gold and crude oil prices, albeit with certain lags.

Wang et al. (2020) investigated the impact of economic policy uncertainty (EPU)⁸ on Bitcoin against GBP and USD, and indicated that its returns were significantly higher on days with highest EPU compared to on days with lowest EPU. It was also observed that the US EPU, but not UK EPU, increased volatility and trading volume after the top 5% highest EPU days, and there were spillover effects from the US to the UK market.

Mahfooz and Phillips (2024) trained long short-term memory (LSTM) and Facebook Prophet models using historical Bitcoin prices and exogenous variables, concluding that LSTM outperformed Facebook Prophet, and that including the US interest rate and recession probability significantly improved the models' capability for forecasting future Bitcoin prices.

2.1.2 Market microstructure

Market microstructure mainly consists of two parts: first, financial factors, including Bitcoin's historical price and volume, and the corresponding technical indicators such as moving averages and Bollinger bands; second, factors reflecting blockchain activities, such as hash rate and difficulty.

Ciaian et al. (2016) analyzed the impact of market forces of supply, which was captured by the stock of Bitcoin in circulation, and demand, which was represented by the number of transactions and addresses, and found that the market forces of supply and demand had a strong impact on Bitcoin price, especially the demand side.

Kristoufek (2015) also concluded that trade usage, money supply and price level influenced Bitcoin's long-term price. Besides, he investigated the technical drivers and concluded that rising Bitcoin prices initially motivated users to become miners, but this effect diminished over time due to specialized mining hardware increasing hash rates

⁸ <http://www.policyuncertainty.com>

and difficulty. This reflected a typical market response to profit opportunities, with a reversal observed at the end of the study period.

Georgoula et al. (2015) offered empirical evidence to the Bitcoin price boost effect of hash rate, which is expected because the hash rate reflects mining difficulty and marginal production costs, exerting upward pressure on Bitcoin's market value.

Balcilar et al. (2017) found that under normal market conditions, traded volume predicted Bitcoin returns, offering valuable insights to investors. However, during strong or weak market phases, past values were the sole predictor of future returns, diminishing the relevance of volume information.

2.1.3 Investors' attention and interest

Kristoufek (2013) found a bidirectional relationship between Bitcoin prices and interest, measured by Google Trends and Wikipedia visits. Prices and search queries influenced each other, driving speculation and frequent bubbles.

Garcia et al. (2014) investigated Bitcoin bubbles by analyzing investors' social media activities on Twitter (now X) and Facebook, search queries on Google and Wikipedia, and user adoption traced from the Bitcoin blockchain and the daily number of downloads of the official Bitcoin software client from the SourceForge platform. They identified two positive feedback loops: a social cycle in which rising search volume and social media activity elevated Bitcoin prices, and a user adoption cycle in which new users entering the transaction network drove prices higher. It was also observed that spikes in search volume often preceded market downturns.

Georgoula et al. (2015) employed support vector machines (SVM) to analyze daily Twitter (now X) sentiment regarding Bitcoin and found that higher Twitter (now X) sentiment correlated positively with short-term increases in Bitcoin prices. Increased Wikipedia search queries for Bitcoin were also found associated with higher market prices, indicating greater public interest driving price movements.

Ciaian et al. (2016) tested structural breaks in Bitcoin price series and offered a more nuanced observation: when Bitcoin was little known, Wikipedia visits had a stronger impact on its price than when it became more established on financial markets. In the long term, views on Wikipedia should have no impact on Bitcoin price, because the

information on Wikipedia would be rather basic and should be known for most investors over time. The number of new members and new posts on online Bitcoin forums were also tested. Similar to the Wikipedia visits, the number of new members only influenced Bitcoin price in the short run. On the contrary, the number of new posts preserved a strong impact on Bitcoin price in the long term.

Matta et al. (2015) analyzed the relationship between Bitcoin price movements and the volume of related tweets, the volume of tweets with a positive sentiment, and Google Trends data. They concluded that positive tweets could serve as predictors for Bitcoin price movements within 3-4 days, while Google Trends was even more effective, exhibiting a high cross-correlation value of 0.64 with no delay.

2.1.4 Most important factors for Bitcoin price prediction

John et al. (2024) systematically reviewed academic research on cryptocurrency price prediction from 2014 to 2024 and identified four key parameters: (1) historical price and volume data, including opening, high, low, closing (OHLC) prices, average prices, and trading volumes; (2) technical indicators, such as simple and exponential moving averages; (3) blockchain features, such as transaction fees and miners' revenue; and (4) social media sentiment on Twitter (now X). This conclusion largely aligns with the literature review presented above.

Additionally, this study also considered the impact of macroeconomic indicators on Bitcoin prices. This is because, firstly, some studies have shown (strong) correlations between them, and secondly, as Bitcoin becomes more mainstream, the importance of this type of indicators is likely to increase. For details on the final selection of features used in this study, please refer to the section on data collection and preprocessing.

2.2 Predictive models

2.2.1 Machine learning models

Sharang and Rao (2015) created a medium frequency trading strategy for a portfolio of 5-year and 10-year US Treasury note futures. They treated this as a classification task, forecasting weekly directional movements using features derived from a deep belief network trained on technical indicators of the portfolio. Their approach, experimenting with SVM, logistic regression and neural networks, achieved 5-10% higher accuracy

and significantly higher PNL compared to random prediction methods.

In addition, machine learning methods have been extensively used for stock price prediction. For example, Wang and Choi (2013) used SVM to predict the movement directions of the constituents in the Korea Composite Stock Price Index (KOSPI) and the Hang Seng Index (HSI), achieving notably high hit ratios. Lauretto et al. (2013) obtained promising results using random forests for advising trade operations in the BM&F/BOVESPA stock market. Researchers not only apply machine learning but also fine-tune and combine different machine learning methods to achieve better performance. For example, Huang et al. (2005) studied the ability to predict the weekly movement direction of the NIKKEI 225 index using SVM. Although SVM surpassed all the comparison methods in forecasting accuracy, including random walk, linear discriminant analysis, quadratic discriminant analysis and Elman backpropagation neural networks, the integrated model combining SVM with the other classifiers demonstrated superior forecasting performance compared to all individual methods.

There have also been many studies applying machine learning to cryptocurrency price prediction, particularly for Bitcoin.

Maden et al. (2015) implemented two phases to predict Bitcoin price using machine-learning algorithms. In the first phase, they performed three binomial classification algorithms, GLM, SVM, and random forest, on daily data of Bitcoin price and 16 additional features about the Bitcoin network and market, achieving an accuracy of 98.79% in predicting the sign of the daily price change with GLM, and 94.98% with random forest. In the second phase, they compared GLM and random forest on 10-second and 10-minute interval Bitcoin price data, concluding that random forest on 10-minute interval data achieved the best accuracy rate of 57.40%.

Colianni et al. (2015) developed three supervised machine learning techniques, Naive Bayes, logistic regression and SVM, to predict whether Bitcoin price would increase or decrease using related Twitter (now X) data. After rigorous data cleaning and error analysis, they achieved 95% day-to-day prediction accuracy with Naive Bayes, and 98.58% hour-to-hour prediction accuracy with logistic regression.

Rahman et al. (2018) implemented 5 regression algorithms, including Multiple Linear

Regression, Polynomial Regression, Support Vector Regression, Decision Tree Regression and Random Tree Regression, and 11 classification algorithms, including Logistic Regression, K-Nearest Neighbour, SVM, Kernel SVM, Naive Bayes, Decision Tree Classification, Random Forrest Classification, Artificial Neural Network, Principle Component Analysis, Linear Discriminant Analysis and Kernel PCA to predict Bitcoin price change based on social media sentiment. The highest accuracy percentage achieved was 89.65% with Naive Bayes, followed by 85.78% with Random Forest Classification.

Because machine learning algorithms can easily detect trends and patterns, they are very effective for predictive analysis. However, compared to traditional machine learning, deep learning excels in handling complex data and automatic feature extraction, allowing it to learn and model higher-level features and patterns automatically. Due to the superior performance demonstrated by deep learning in many studies, as discussed below, this paper focuses on deep learning models.

2.2.2 Deep learning models

Deep learning offers remarkable accuracy because of its advanced skills in detecting complex patterns and nonlinear relationships, excels at processing unstructured data, and possesses the capability to learn continuously and adapt to evolving conditions.

Recurrent neural networks (RNNs) outperform traditional multilayer perceptrons (MLPs) in sequential data tasks by effectively capturing temporal dependencies, handling variable-length sequences, and preserving context through their dynamic hidden states. However, due to the vanishing gradient issue in RNNs, long short-term memory (LSTM) networks have been introduced to retain both short-term and long-term memory through specialized gates. LSTMs are effective tools for processing complex, non-linear, and non-stationary financial time series. Gated recurrent units (GRUs) are an alternative to the more complex LSTM networks, aiming to simplify the architecture while maintaining comparable performance across various tasks. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are another popular approach for time series data analysis, especially in feature extraction and pattern recognition. They are often employed together with sequential data processors such as LSTM and GRU networks.

These deep learning models and their variants or optimizations are widely applied in financial time series forecasting. Below are some representative studies.

Maknickienė and Maknickas (2012) treated neural networks as AI-experts and the respective generated predictions as their professional decisions. By developing eight Evolino-LSTM networks as eight experts and employing expert information processing techniques such as the Delphi method and prediction compatibility, the final trading model for EUR/USD rates achieved up to 4% profit.

Di Persio and Honchar (2016) applied MLP, CNN and RNN to forecast the trend movements of the S&P500 index, and concluded CNN, especially their novel approach Wavelet+CNN, to be the best model for financial time series.

Nelson et al. (2017) predicted future prices of different stocks from the Brazilian stock exchange (Bovespa) with different machine learning methods such as LSTM, MLP and Random Forest, and investment strategies such as buy and hold. They concluded that the LSTM model outperformed the other models and strategies, achieving promising results with up to 55.90% accuracy.

Kim and Won (2018) combined LSTM with one to three GARCH-type models (GARCH, EGARCH, EWMA) to forecast KOSPI 200 index volatility. Results showed that hybrid models with multiple GARCH models significantly improved prediction performance. The GEW-LSTM model, combining all three GARCH models, had the lowest prediction errors and outperformed both single hybrid models and standalone models. Furthermore, LSTM-based hybrid models consistently showed lower out-of-sample forecast errors compared to DFN-based models. The EGARCH model had the best performance among GARCH-type models, followed by GARCH and EWMA, with hybrid models reflecting this performance ranking.

Alongside traditional market variables such as stock price and trading volume, Zhang et al. (2021) incorporated traditional attention variables such as the extreme return and the abnormal trading volume for each stock, as well as new attention variables such as the number of Baidu news for each stock and the abnormal Baidu search volume, as additional inputs to their LSTM models for forecasting stock prices. Their findings showed that these attention proxies enhanced the LSTM's prediction accuracy.

Many deep learning studies have also focused on predicting Bitcoin prices. Greaves and Au (2015) investigated Bitcoin blockchain network-based features to predict Bitcoin price movements using Logistic Regression, SVM and ANN. The best classifier was the ANN, a regular 2-hidden-layer feed-forward neural network, which achieved an accuracy of 55.10%.

McNally et al. (2018) developed a Bayesian optimized RNN and an LSTM network to predict the direction of Bitcoin price. The non-linear deep learning models outperformed the benchmark ARIMA, and the LSTM achieved the highest classification accuracy of 52.78% among the models tested.

In addition to historical Bitcoin prices, volume and blockchain information, Jang and Lee (2018) further considered macroeconomic variables such as S&P 500, Eurostoxx, DOW 30, NASDAQ, crude oil, SSE, Gold, VIX, Nikkei 225 and FTSE 100, and exchange rates such as GBP/USD, JPY/USD, CHF/USD, CNY/USD and EUR/USD. They compared three prediction models, Linear Regression, Support Vector Regression (SVR) and Bayesian Neural Network (BNN), and found that the BNN model outperformed the other two in predicting Bitcoin prices.

Ji et al. (2019) compared the Bitcoin price prediction performances of DNN, LSTM, CNN, Deep Residual Network (ResNet), CRNN (a combination of CNN and RNN), and Ensemble (DNN, LSTM and CNN at the 1st level and another DNN at the 2nd level), and concluded that LSTM performed slightly better than the other models when Bitcoin price prediction was set as a regression problem, while DNN performed slightly better when Bitcoin price prediction was set as a classification problem. Interestingly, they also conducted a profitability analysis, ending up with every classification model generating a small profit, whereas every regression model resulted in a loss.

Kumar et al. (2023) developed an LSTM-based RNN to predict the Bitcoin price for the next day based on the prices of the previous 30 days. The batch size was set to 11, the number of epochs was 30, and the initial weight was zero. As the learning process continued, the loss decreased at a slower pace and eventually stabilized, indicating a low risk of overfitting.

Wang et al. (2022) combined direct (Google Trends and Tweets) and indirect attention

proxies such as the extreme return and the abnormal trading volume of Bitcoin, with Bitcoin trading data, and found that the LSTM's prediction accuracy improved significantly. They concluded that attention variables enhanced forecasting more than historical data alone, especially the direct attention proxies, and thus, integrating these measures optimized LSTM's ability to predict Bitcoin returns.

Based on the assumption that attention mechanisms enable deep learning models to concentrate on pertinent data, thereby enhancing their accuracy and efficiency, Ladhari and Boubaker (2024) developed a LSTM-Attention model and successfully achieved an accuracy of 99.84% in predicting Bitcoin prices.

Aggarwal et al. (2019) conducted a comparative study on various parameters affecting Bitcoin price prediction using CNN, LSTM, and GRU, based on root mean square error (RMSE), and concluded that the deep learning models were evidently effective for predicting Bitcoin prices. When considering Bitcoin-related parameters for price prediction, the LSTM model achieved the lowest RMSE value. But when gold prices were used as a parameter for Bitcoin price prediction, none of the three models showed a positive correlation between gold prices and Bitcoin prices, and the actual versus predicted Bitcoin price graph showed significant deviations. However, different settings were used for different models: the number of layers for CNN was 2, the number of layers for LSTM was 4, and the number of layers for GRU was 1. Therefore, even though the LSTM model performed the best in this study, it is difficult to definitively say that LSTM is superior to CNN and GRU.

Dutta et al. (2020) concluded that recurrent neural networks, such as LSTM and GRU, performed better than traditional machine learning models. When dealing with limited data, neural networks like LSTM and GRU could effectively adjust past information and learn from non-linear patterns. In their study, the GRU model, with its simplicity, where forgetting and updating occur simultaneously, outperformed the LSTM model, proving to be particularly effective for Bitcoin price prediction. Moreover, they also found that adding recurrent dropout could further enhance the performance of the GRU architecture.

Awoke et al. (2020) also reached similar conclusions, finding that both LSTM and GRU

models were more capable of recognizing long-term dependencies, and that compared to the LSTM model, the GRU model performed better in Bitcoin price prediction and had a shorter compilation time.

In summary, among the deep learning models used for processing financial time series data and predicting future prices, CNN, LSTM and GRU, especially the LSTM model, play a significant role. Many researchers have achieved promising results using these models through various methods such as feature engineering, data processing and model tuning. Therefore, in terms of model selection, considering the characteristics of Bitcoin's financial time series, this study focuses primarily on the application of the LSTM model for Bitcoin price prediction while also examining the performance of the GRU model.

2.2.3 Hybrid deep learning models

There are many types of hybrid models, incorporating various combinations of classic econometric and statistical models, machine learning models, and deep learning models. This paper focuses on deep learning models, and therefore, the combination of econometric and statistical models or machine learning models with deep learning models is considered as fine-tuning of the latter. In this section, hybrid deep learning models are defined as models that involve only combinations of different deep learning models. The following are some representative related studies.

Livieris et al. (2020) introduced a hybrid CNN-LSTM model for predicting gold prices. It combined convolutional layers for feature extraction from time-series data with LSTM layers for capturing short and long-term dependencies. Comparisons with other models such as SVR and standalone LSTM showed that the hybrid CNN-LSTM significantly improved forecasting performance.

Islam and Hossain (2021) introduced a hybrid GRU-LSTM model for predicting FOREX currency prices. It combined a GRU layer (20 neurons) and an LSTM layer (256 neurons) to forecast prices at 10-minute and 30-minute intervals. Compared to a standalone GRU model, a standalone LSTM model and a simple moving average (SMA) based statistical model, the hybrid GRU-LSTM consistently outperformed in accuracy metrics and demonstrated lower risk in currency price forecasting.

In research on Bitcoin, popular combinations include CNN and LSTM, CNN and GRU, as well as LSTM and GRU hybrids. Li and Dai (2020) proposed a hybrid neural network model based on CNN for feature extraction and LSTM for time series learning. The input data consisted of internal Bitcoin transaction data, as well as external macroeconomic variables and investor attention data. Their experimental results showed that the hybrid model outperformed the single-structure neural networks, including BP, CNN, and LSTM.

Guo et al. (2021) further developed a novel hybrid model called MRC-LSTM, which combined LSTM with a Multi-scale Residual Convolutional (MRC) neural network. They compared it with different models, including MLP, CNN, LSTM and CNN-LSTM. After processing multiple transaction information, macroeconomic variables and investor attention factors, and conducting repeated experiments, they concluded that the MRC-LSTM achieved the best performance in forecasting Bitcoin prices.

Ali et al. (2023) developed an ensemble model that combined CNN and GRU to jointly identify spatial patterns and temporal dynamics. The results indicated that this ensemble CNN-GRU model demonstrated exceptional predictive capabilities, achieving high R-squared scores, including 0.99 for Bitcoin and Ethereum, and 0.98 for Ripple.

Kervanci et al. (2023) used LSTM, GRU and hybrid LSTM-GRU models to predict Bitcoin prices. They applied hyperparameter optimization methods such as Bayesian Optimization (BO), random search and grid search. The results showed that the hybrid LSTM-GRU model with BO outperformed all other methods in this study and in their reviewed literature in terms of MAE, MSE and RMSE.

In summary, hybrid deep learning models combine multiple predictive models to leverage the strengths of individual models while mitigating their limitations and weaknesses, thereby improving overall performance. Before 2020, the LSTM model held a dominant position in Bitcoin price prediction research. However, since 2020, various hybrid models have been proposed and reported to achieve superior performance compared to single deep learning models. Researchers are increasingly moving towards models that integrate multiple deep learning techniques to attain the best prediction results (John et al., 2024). Therefore, this study also developed LSTM-

GRU hybrid models and GRU-LSTM hybrid models, and compared them with individual LSTM and GRU models.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research design

The purpose of this study is to use deep learning models to predict Bitcoin prices. The detailed research process is as follows:

Step 1: Determine the specific deep learning models to employ. By reviewing existing relevant studies, the primary deep learning models focused on in this research were LSTM, GRU and their hybrid models.

Step 2: Determine which inputs to feed into the models. Through reviewing existing research and conducting data analysis and processing, the input features and target value for the models were identified. The target value was set as Bitcoin's daily closing price, and the specific selection and processing of features are detailed in the data collection and preprocessing section.

Step 3: Train and evaluate an LSTM model. This step was further divided into three sub-steps. First, the LSTM model was tuned to obtain the optimal hyperparameters. Next, the model was trained using these optimal hyperparameters, and the best model state was recorded. Finally, the saved best model was applied to the test set, and the model's performance was ultimately evaluated using the test set.

Step 4: Using the best hyperparameters obtained from tuning the LSTM model, directly construct a single GRU model, an LSTM-GRU hybrid model and a GRU-LSTM hybrid model, and compare the performance of each model under the same hyperparameter configuration.

Step 5: Train and evaluate a GRU model using the same method as in step 3.

Step 6: Using the best hyperparameters obtained from tuning the GRU model, directly construct a single LSTM model, an LSTM-GRU hybrid model and a GRU-LSTM hybrid model, and compare the performance of each model under the same hyperparameter configuration.

Step 7: Train and evaluate an LSTM-GRU hybrid model using the same method as in

step 3.

Step 8: Using the best hyperparameters obtained from tuning the LSTM-GRU hybrid model, directly construct a single LSTM model, a single GRU model, and a GRU-LSTM hybrid model, and compare the performance of each model under the same hyperparameter configuration.

Step 9: Train and evaluate a GRU-LSTM hybrid model using the same method as in step 3.

Step 10: Using the best hyperparameters obtained from tuning the GRU-LSTM hybrid model, directly construct a single LSTM model, a single GRU model, and an LSTM-GRU hybrid model, and compare the performance of each model under the same hyperparameter configuration.

Finally, compare the performances of all the models obtained from the above steps and draw conclusions.

3.2 Deep learning models

Deep learning models have advantages in handling complex and unstructured large-scale data. Though CNNs are best suited for image processing and computer vision tasks, they can also be applied to time series data by unrolling the series into a 1D vector and then using 1D convolution on this vector instead of the 2D convolution used for image data. CNNs' positive performance on such tasks has also been verified by studies like the research of Di Persio and Honchar (2016). However, a drawback of these methods is their impracticality for handling arbitrarily long sequences, where RNNs hold an advantage. RNNs are effective for making predictions from sequential data, particularly when dealing with sequences of varying lengths. But RNNs face significant obstacles due to vanishing and exploding gradient problems. These issues are exacerbated in RNNs because the gradient must traverse a large number of timesteps when using backpropagation through time (BPTT) along with weight sharing across those timesteps.

To tackle these challenges, advanced variations of RNNs, such as long short-term memory (LSTM) and gated recurrent units (GRUs), have been developed. LSTMs and GRUs introduce gating mechanisms that regulate the flow of information, making it

easier for the network to learn long-term dependencies. These architectures have demonstrated significant improvements in performance across a variety of sequential tasks. LSTM, proposed by Hochreiter and Schmidhuber (1997) and improved by Gers et al. (2000), introduces self-loops, allowing the gradient to flow over extended periods. And the weight of this self-loop is context-dependent rather than fixed. By gating the self-loop weight, the time scale of integration can be dynamically adjusted. This allows an LSTM even with fixed parameters to vary its integration time scale based on the input sequence, as the time constants are determined by the model itself. Due to the complex architecture of LSTM, GRU was introduced by Cho et al. (2014) to simplify the computation and implementation while keeping the essence and advancement of the LSTM model. Compared to LSTM, GRU does not possess an internal cell state, and it merges the forget and remember gates into one update gate. Although additional variations and further simplifications have been explored, LSTM and GRU still remain unmatched by competitors (Goodfellow et al., 2017, Ekman, 2022). Thus, this paper focuses on LSTM and GRU models.

3.2.1 Long short-term memory (LSTM)

LSTM was designed to address the vanishing and exploding gradient problems encountered when training standard RNNs on long sequences of data. By incorporating memory cells and gating mechanisms, LSTMs can effectively capture long-range dependencies and are highly effective for time series prediction tasks.

An LSTM network consists of a series of LSTM cells, and each cell contains three important components: the forget gate, the input gate, and the output gate. The forget gate $f^{(t)}$ determines which information should be removed from the internal cell state. It processes the previous hidden state and the current input, producing a value between 0 and 1. The input gate $i^{(t)}$ together with the candidate update function $\tilde{C}^{(t)}$ decides which new information should be stored in the cell state. After these processes, the old cell state $C^{(t-1)}$ is updated to the new cell state $C^{(t)}$. Finally, the output gate $o^{(t)}$ controls the LSTM cell's output $h^{(t)}$, which will serve as the hidden state for the subsequent cell in the next timestep. The following presents the two most common ways to describe how LSTM works: one in equation form (Equation 1) and the other in figure form (Figure

1).

Equation 1. Equations describing an LSTM cell (Ekman, 2022)

Forget gate: $f^{(t)} = \sigma(W_f [h^{(t-1)}, x^{(t)}] + b_f)$ Input gate: $i^{(t)} = \sigma(W_i [h^{(t-1)}, x^{(t)}] + b_i)$ Candidate update function: $\tilde{C}^{(t)} = \tanh(W_c [h^{(t-1)}, x^{(t)}] + b_c)$ Cell state: $C^{(t)} = f^{(t)} * C^{(t-1)} + i^{(t)} * \tilde{C}^{(t)}$ Output gate: $o^{(t)} = \sigma(W_o [h^{(t-1)}, x^{(t)}] + b_o)$ The output of the cell: $h^{(t)} = o^{(t)} * \tanh(C^{(t)})$

Figure 1. LSTM cells unrolled in time⁹

3.2.2 Gated recurrent unit (GRU)

Similar to LSTM, GRU also employs gating mechanisms to dynamically regulate the flow of information, facilitating the effective capture of long-range dependencies. The primary distinction from LSTM is that GRU combines the forgetting factor and state update decision into a single gating unit, which allows it to achieve competitive performance with fewer parameters.

A GRU consists of two primary gates: the reset gate and the update gate. The reset gate r_j of the j -th hidden unit determines how much information from the previous hidden state $h_j^{(t-1)}$ should be forgotten or retained by the candidate hidden state $\tilde{h}_j^{(t)}$. And the update gate z_j decides how the current hidden state $h_j^{(t)}$ should be influenced by the previous hidden state $h_j^{(t-1)}$ and the candidate hidden state $\tilde{h}_j^{(t)}$. The following presents the corresponding equations that describe how GRU works (Equation 2).

⁹ <https://colah.github.io/posts/2015-08-Understanding-LSTMs>

Equation 2. Equations describing a GRU (Cho et al., 2014)

Reset gate: $r_j = \sigma([W_r x^{(t)}]_j + [U_r h^{(t-1)}]_j)$ Update gate: $z_j = \sigma([W_z x^{(t)}]_j + [U_z h^{(t-1)}]_j)$ Candidate hidden state: $\tilde{h}_j^{(t)} = \tanh([W_x x^{(t)}]_j + [U(r * h^{(t-1)})]_j)$ Current hidden state: $h_j^{(t)} = z_j h_j^{(t-1)} + (1 - z_j) \tilde{h}_j^{(t)}$

3.2.3 Model architecture in this paper

Given that most existing studies have used a 2-layer LSTM, which is sufficient for a time series task to capture nonlinear relationships in the data (McNally et al., 2018), this study also constructed a 2-layer LSTM model with each layer attached to a dropout layer to minimize overfitting. To facilitate better comparison between different models, the same model architecture was employed for all the four deep learning models: LSTM, GRU, LSTM-GRU and GRU-LSTM. As shown in Figure 2, the architectures of all models are illustrated.

Figure 2. Model architecture

3.3 Fine-tuning method

In this study, the Optuna library was used to automatically optimize the hyperparameter selection for the deep learning models. Optuna is a software framework for automating

hyperparameter optimization, specifically designed for machine learning applications. It performs hyperparameter search primarily based on the idea of Bayesian optimization, with the default algorithm being TPE (Tree-structured Parzen Estimator)¹⁰. Compared to manual tuning, automatic tuning is more efficient and comprehensive, effectively improving model performance.

3.4 Evaluation metrics

Although Bitcoin price prediction can be treated as a classification problem, where model performance is evaluated based on whether the directions predicted by deep learning models match the directions of the actual price movements, this study approached it as a regression problem. Specifically, it used deep learning models to predict the exact price values of Bitcoin. Therefore, this study employed mean squared error (MSE), root mean squared error (RMSE), mean absolute error (MAE), mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), and R-squared (R^2) as evaluation metrics. These metrics are commonly used to assess the difference between predicted values and real (target) values, and a brief introduction to each of them is provided below.

3.4.1 Mean squared error (MSE)

Mean squared error (MSE) is a widely employed metric for evaluating the precision of a regression model. It calculates the average of the squared differences between the actual closing prices of Bitcoin and the corresponding predicted values created by a deep learning model. The smaller the value of MSE, the better the performance of the model. MSE is very useful because it squares the errors, which means that larger errors are penalized more heavily than smaller ones. This characteristic makes the metric particularly sensitive to outliers. However, this sensitivity can also result in MSE disproportionately highlighting the impact of these outliers, potentially leading to an exaggerated error measurement. MSE is calculated as follows:

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$$

where:

¹⁰ https://optuna.readthedocs.io/en/stable/tutorial/10_key_features/003_efficient_optimization_algorithms.html

y_i is the actual Bitcoin closing price of the i th day or observation,

\hat{y}_i is the predicted Bitcoin price for the i th day or observation,

n is the total number of days or observations.

3.4.2 Root mean squared error (RMSE)

Root mean squared error (RMSE) is the square root of the MSE. It provides an error metric in the same units as the original data, which makes it easier to understand. RMSE retains the benefits of MSE in terms of penalizing larger errors more harshly but at the same time also provides better interpretability. It is particularly valuable for comparing different deep learning models, as it offers a straightforward measure of average error magnitude. RMSE is more convenient than MSE when an error metric needs to be expressed in the same units as the original data. The formula for RMSE is as follows:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}$$

3.4.3 Mean absolute error (MAE)

Mean absolute error (MAE) represents the average magnitude of the errors between the actual Bitcoin prices and their corresponding predicted values, without considering their direction. It is the average of the absolute differences between real prices and predicted values. MAE is less sensitive to outliers compared to MSE and RMSE, because it does not square the errors. Instead, it treats all errors equally, making it a robust metric for evaluating model performance when the objective is to minimize the average error without overstating the influence of large deviations. MAE can be very beneficial in situations where a straightforward interpretation of the average error magnitude is needed. The formula for MAE is as follows:

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i|$$

3.4.4 Mean absolute percentage error (MAPE)

Mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) is a scale-independent metric, because it evaluates prediction performance as a percentage of the actual values. This relative measure of deviation is particularly useful for comparing model performance across

different studies, as it allows for comparison despite variations in data scales. However, MAPE has certain limitations, for example, it can be undefined or highly unstable when actual values y_i are close to zero, as the relative error can become excessively large. Additionally, MAPE is sensitive to the scale of the actual values, which can lead to misleading conclusions if the data includes extreme values or zeros. Despite these limitations, MAPE should be effective for assessing Bitcoin price prediction, as this study does not include Bitcoin's very low early prices, and the evaluation metrics encompass both relative error values and absolute error values. The formula for MAPE is as follows:

$$\text{MAPE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{y_i - \hat{y}_i}{y_i} \right|$$

3.4.5 R-squared (R^2)

R-squared (R^2), also known as the coefficient of determination, quantifies the proportion of the variance of the dependent variable that is explained by the independent variables in the model. The value of R^2 ranges from 0 to 1, where 0 indicates that the model explains none of the variance of the dependent variable, and 1 indicates that the model explains all the variance. Generally speaking, a higher R^2 value suggests a better fit of the model. However, R^2 alone does not tell the whole story, as it does not account for overfitting and can sometimes be misleading when comparing models with different numbers of predictors. Given that this study uses the same features and datasets for different models, R^2 should be able to provide effective insights for model comparison. R^2 is calculated as follows:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}$$

where:

\bar{y} is the mean of the observed values.

4. Data collection and preprocessing

4.1 Data collection

4.1.1 Bitcoin historical prices and technical indicators

Since the ultimate goal of Bitcoin price prediction is practical trading, particularly for relatively active and frequent financial transactions, the Bitcoin prices used in this study were sourced from Binance, the leading exchange at present¹¹. As Binance only started providing data from August 17, 2017, the time frame for all data in this study ranged from August 17, 2017 (the date Binance began trading) to July 31, 2024 (the date near the conclusion of this study), covering a total of 2,541 days.

After obtaining Bitcoin's open, high, low, close, and volume (OHLCV) data from Binance (<https://data-api.binance.vision/api/v1/klines>), the following technical indicators were calculated for further analysis: SMA, EMA, RSI, MACD and Bollinger Bands. These indicators are considered among the most powerful and commonly used tools in financial analysis, particularly for trading and price prediction.

4.1.2 Blockchain data

Since Bitcoin is a blockchain asset, it makes sense to assume that blockchain-related data can provide valuable information for predicting its price, which has been confirmed in previous studies. Referring to the previously reviewed papers, data on transaction fees, miners' revenue, hash rate and difficulty was obtained from Blockchain.com, one of the oldest and most popular on-chain data platforms (<https://api.blockchain.info/charts>).

4.1.3 Macroeconomic factors

Several macroeconomic factors have been shown in previous studies to be (highly) related to Bitcoin's prices. As Bitcoin gains increasing recognition in the market, especially with the issuance of multiple Bitcoin ETFs this year, such as the iShares Bitcoin Trust ETF (IBIT) from BlackRock, along with the commitment of US presidential candidate Trump to include Bitcoin as part of the national strategic reserve if elected, the mainstream acceptance of Bitcoin may enhance its interaction with other

¹¹ <https://coinmarketcap.com/rankings/exchanges> (08.2024)

macroeconomic factors. Therefore, the influence of macroeconomic factors on Bitcoin prices may grow larger in the future. Based on the previously reviewed papers, the following data was obtained from Yahoo Finance (yfinance): gold (GC=F), oil (CL=F), USD index (DX-Y.NYB), S&P 500 (^GSPC), and NASDAQ (^IXIC).

4.1.4 Investors' attention and interest

Investors' attention and interest are also important factors influencing Bitcoin's prices. However, the impact of this kind of factors on Bitcoin varies greatly depending on the time period. In the early stages of Bitcoin's existence, many people did not know what Bitcoin was, so data from Google searches and Wikipedia could provide insights into the increase in the number of people interested in Bitcoin. As Bitcoin became more widely known, the influence of searching and browsing data from these websites on Bitcoin's prices weakened. Some studies have demonstrated that the number of related tweets on Twitter (now X), particularly those with positive sentiment, could help predict Bitcoin's prices. However, since Musk took over Twitter (now X), access to related data has been significantly restricted (John et al., 2024). Additionally, as Bitcoin becomes more and more mainstream, data from X, one of the key social platforms in the cryptocurrency industry, may only reflect a partial view of Bitcoin-related trends in the future. Nevertheless, this study obtained and merged Google Trends data from pytrends using the keywords "Bitcoin", "bitcoin", "BTC" and "btc" for further analysis.

4.2 Data preprocessing

4.2.1 Feature analysis and selection

The 32 features collected above were analyzed for correlation with the target variable: the daily closing price of Bitcoin. The results of the correlation analysis are shown in the figure 3 below. The warmer the color and the closer the value to 100, the higher the correlation; conversely, the cooler the color and the closer the value to 0, the lower the correlation.

Figure 3. Correlation analysis of features

According to the correlation analysis, the following features were deleted due to their low correlations with Bitcoin's daily closing price: the daily Google search trend volume index (Google_Trends: -0.022363), the daily trading volume of Bitcoin (Volume: -0.012976), the relative strength index (RSI: 0.058699), the USD exchange rate index (USD Index: 0.207470), momentum indicators (MACD: 0.247704 and MACD_Signal: 0.262528), on-chain transaction fees (Transaction Fees: 0.329673), and oil price (Oil: 0.490855).

Since there were already Bitcoin's daily OHLC prices, the 5-day EMA and SMA capturing ultra-short-term price fluctuations were deleted to prevent feature redundancy. To capture short-term and medium-term price fluctuations while preventing feature redundancy, the 10-day and 20-day EMA were retained, while the 10-day and 20-day SMA were removed. To identify medium-term and long-term trends and prevent feature redundancy, the 50-day and 100-day SMA were retained, while the 50-day and 100-day

EMA were deleted. Given that there were only 2,541 days of data totally, using the 200-day EMA and SMA would result in missing data for the first 199 days. Considering the amount of data available for deep learning model training, the 200-day EMA and SMA were not considered.

Finally, there were 16 features for the deep learning model training: Bitcoin's daily opening, highest, lowest and closing prices, 10-day and 20-day EMA, Bollinger Bands, 50-day and 100-day SMA, miners' revenue, difficulty, hash rate, NASDAQ, S&P 500 and gold price. The details of feature analysis and selection are presented in table 1.

Table 1. Feature analysis and selection

Features	Correlation	Description
OHLCV		
Close	1.000000	The daily closing price of Bitcoin
High	0.999341	The daily highest price of Bitcoin
Low	0.999152	The daily lowest price of Bitcoin
Open	0.998507	The daily opening price of Bitcoin
Volume	-0.012976	The daily trading volume of Bitcoin (deleted due to low correlation)
Technical Indicators		
EMA_5	0.998849	5-day exponential moving average (deleted to prevent feature redundancy)
SMA_5	0.998309	5-day simple moving average (deleted to prevent feature redundancy)
EMA_10	0.997030	10-day exponential moving average
SMA_10	0.995821	10-day simple moving average (deleted to prevent feature redundancy)
EMA_20	0.993136	20-day exponential moving average
SMA_20	0.990621	20-day simple moving average (deleted to prevent feature redundancy)
Bollinger_Upper	0.989005	The upper band of Bollinger Bands
Bollinger_Lower	0.981376	The lower band of Bollinger Bands
EMA_50	0.980223	50-day exponential moving average (deleted to prevent feature redundancy)
SMA_50	0.972788	50-day simple moving average
EMA_100	0.958217	100-day exponential moving average (deleted to prevent feature redundancy)
SMA_100	0.937473	100-day simple moving average
EMA_200	0.916045	200-day exponential moving average (deleted considering available data amount)
SMA_200	0.874203	200-day simple moving average (deleted considering available data amount)
MACD_Signal	0.262528	The 9-day exponential moving average of the MACD line (deleted due to low correlation)
MACD	0.247704	12-day and 26-day exponential moving average convergence divergence (deleted due to low correlation)
RSI	0.058699	Relative Strength Index (deleted due to low correlation)
Blockchain Data		
Miners Revenue	0.873713	Miners' daily revenue in USD
Difficulty	0.705719	Measurement of how challenging to find a new block and earn rewards
Hash Rate	0.698312	The total computational power used by miners on the Bitcoin blockchain
Transaction Fees	0.329673	On-chain transaction fees in USD (deleted due to low correlation)

Macroeconomic Factors

NASDAQ	0.914073	An American stock exchange index focusing on technology and growth-oriented companies
S&P 500	0.900862	A stock market index measuring the performance of 500 largest publicly traded companies in the US
Gold	0.766162	The price of gold futures contracts
Oil	0.490855	The price of crude oil futures contracts (deleted due to low correlation)
USD Index	0.207470	The value of the USD relative to a basket of major foreign currencies (deleted due to low correlation)

Investors' attention/interest

Google_Trends	-0.022363	The daily Google search trend volume index (deleted due to low correlation)
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4.2.2 Data cleaning and splitting

Since the data from August 17, 2017 to November 23, 2017 (the first 99 days) did not have a 100-day SMA, feeding it into a deep learning model would cause errors. Therefore, all data from this period was removed. The final dataset spanned from November 24, 2017 to July 31, 2024, totaling 2442 days.

Since the stock market and gold futures do not trade on weekends and holidays, the data of NASDAQ, S&P 500 and gold price was missing on these dates. In the real world, the data shown on these dates is from the previous trading day, therefore, the missing values were filled using the previous valid data.

80% of the entire data set was split into the training set, while the remaining 20% was allocated to the test set, resulting in 16 features across 1950 observations for training, and 16 features across the remaining 492 observations for the final test. Figure 4 shows the actual daily closing price movements of Bitcoin across the entire time range covered by this study, as well as how these values as target were divided into the training set and the test set.

Figure 4. Bitcoin’s actual prices as target values

4.3 Statistics summary

Table 2 summarizes the descriptive statistics such as mean, median, standard deviation, minimum and maximum values of all 16 features across 2442 observations. Overall, compared to macroeconomic indicators, Bitcoin’s prices, technical indicators and blockchain features exhibit significant volatility in Bitcoin price movements and the cryptocurrency industry. Meanwhile, short-term and long-term technical indicators indicate that Bitcoin prices are generally on an upward trend.

Table 2. Statistics summary

Features	Obs.	mean	median	std	min	max
Open	2,442	24,935.41	19,533.56	18,879.42	3,211.71	73,072.40
High	2,442	25,551.67	20,056.60	19,319.80	3,276.50	73,777.00
Low	2,442	24,262.07	19,101.86	18,397.03	3,156.26	71,333.31
Close	2,442	24,958.63	19,543.44	18,893.45	3,211.72	73,072.41
EMA_10	2,442	24,851.02	19,650.57	18,752.35	3,399.07	69,465.11
EMA_20	2,442	24,733.55	19,642.82	18,604.17	3,500.41	68,741.41
SMA_50	2,442	24,390.31	19,580.60	18,310.51	3,619.33	67,527.82
SMA_100	2,442	23,773.56	19,002.96	17,612.77	3,678.42	66,752.02
Bollinger_Upper	2,442	27,565.83	21,874.09	20,650.86	3,640.97	77,262.91
Bollinger_Lower	2,442	21,893.61	17,207.79	16,843.02	2,909.39	66,893.45
Miners Revenue	2,442	26,086,332.04	21,404,316.31	15,503,676.28	4,666,604.26	107,755,899.70
Hash Rate	2,442	196,248,594.96	139,433,297.30	168,029,902.91	9,977,010.84	730,072,032.10
Difficulty	2,442	27,012,481,572,482	19,700,000,000,000	22,892,505,047,865	1,350,000,000,000	88,100,000,000,000
Gold	2,442	1,706.06	1,777.75	301.58	1,176.20	2,462.40
S&P 500	2,442	3,712.94	3,819.28	809.36	2,237.40	5,667.20

5. System environment

The experimental hardware and software environment for training the deep learning models in this study was Google Colaboratory, using a Python 3 Google Compute Engine backend, with CPU and 12.7 GB of RAM.

6. Deep learning model training

In existing research, the most popular deep learning model for Bitcoin price prediction was LSTM (John et al., 2024). Therefore, this study started with LSTM to explore how to optimize the model for the most accurate Bitcoin price prediction. Some literature suggested that the GRU model outperformed LSTM, so this study also compared the performance of LSTM and GRU models. Finally, many studies highlighted the superiority of hybrid models, hence this paper explored the effectiveness of an LSTM-GRU hybrid model and a GRU-LSTM model as well.

6.1 LSTM model training

6.1.1 Hyperparameter optimization for LSTM model

The first step was hyperparameter tuning. After importing all necessary libraries and setting a random seed for reproducibility, 16 features across 1950 observations (80% of the total 2442 observations) were loaded and preprocessed to be input into the model. Then, a 2-layer LSTM model with Dropout layers was created, where the hyperparameters would be tuned.

To determine the ranges for the LSTM model's hyperparameters, based on the hyperparameter configurations of existing studies (e.g., Ji et al., 2019; Jay et al., 2020; Tanwar et al., 2021) as well as experimental results, the following hyperparameter search space was established to explore the optimal Bitcoin price prediction model: Early stopping was employed (with patience set to 5), so the number of epochs was always set to 100. The number of time steps was tested with values of 10, 20, 50 and 100, while the batch size was tested with values of 16, 32, 48 and 64. The number of units in the first LSTM layer was set between 30 and 70, with a step of 10. The number

of units in the second LSTM layer was set between 20 and 50, also with a step of 10. The dropout rates for the two Dropout layers were both set between 0.1 and 0.4, with a step of 0.1. There were two optimizer types to choose from: Adam and RMSprop, with learning rates adjustable between $1e-5$ and $1e-2$. A summary of the hyperparameter search space is provided in Table 3.

Table 3. Hyperparameter tuning space summary

Hyperparameter	Tuning Space
Time steps	10, 20, 50, 100
Batch size	16, 32, 48, 64
Units on 1st layer	30, 40, 50, 60, 70
Units on 2nd layer	20, 30, 40, 50
Dropout rate	0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4
Optimizer	Adam, RMSprop
Learning rate	between $1e-5$ and $1e-2$

During the tuning process, TimeSeriesSplit was used to perform five-fold cross-validation on the data. In each fold, the model was trained on the training set and validated on the validation set, and the average validation loss across all folds was returned. This approach aims to evaluate the model's generalization capability as effectively as possible and provide a more stable performance estimate. The MinMaxScaler was applied to scale the training data to the range between 0 and 1, and the validation data on each fold used the scalers of its training data. This approach ensures that the model does not see the validation data during the fitting process, thereby preventing data leakage. The evaluation metric used was mean squared error (MSE), which is a classic and popular metric for this type of tasks. After conducting 80 experiments with different hyperparameter combinations, the best hyperparameter combination was printed for further investigation. The whole optimization process is detailed in Code 1.

Code 1. Hyperparameter optimization code

```
!pip install optuna
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.preprocessing import MinMaxScaler
from sklearn.model_selection import TimeSeriesSplit
import numpy as np
import random
```

```

import os
import tensorflow as tf
from keras.models import Sequential
from keras.layers import LSTM, Dense, Dropout, Input
from keras.callbacks import EarlyStopping
from keras.optimizers import Adam, RMSprop
import optuna
from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error

# Random seed
np.random.seed(42)
random.seed(42)
tf.random.set_seed(42)
os.environ['PYTHONHASHSEED'] = str(42)

# Load data
data = pd.read_csv('Train data.csv')
# Date column as the index
data['Date'] = pd.to_datetime(data['Date'])
data.set_index('Date', inplace=True)

# Set features and target
X = data[['Open', 'High', 'Low', 'Close', 'EMA_10', 'EMA_20', 'SMA_50', 'SMA_100', 'Bollinger_Upper',
          'Bollinger_Lower', 'Miners Revenue', 'Hash Rate', 'Difficulty', 'Gold', 'S&P 500', 'NASDAQ']]
y = data['Close']

# Define time series split
tscv = TimeSeriesSplit(n_splits=5)

# Create sequences
def create_sequences(X, y, timesteps):
    X_sequences = []
    y_sequences = []
    for i in range(len(X) - timesteps):
        X_sequences.append(X[i:i + timesteps])
        y_sequences.append(y[i + timesteps])
    return np.array(X_sequences), np.array(y_sequences)

# Create the LSTM model
def create_lstm_model(timesteps, batch_size, units_layer1, dropout_rate_layer1, units_layer2,
                     dropout_rate_layer2, optimizer_name, learning_rate, input_shape):
    model = Sequential()
    model.add(Input(shape=(timesteps, input_shape)))
    model.add(LSTM(units_layer1, return_sequences=True))
    model.add(Dropout(dropout_rate_layer1))
    model.add(LSTM(units_layer2))
    model.add(Dropout(dropout_rate_layer2))
    model.add(Dense(1))

    # Create optimizer with the specified learning rate
    if optimizer_name == 'adam':

```

```

optimizer = Adam(learning_rate=learning_rate)
elif optimizer_name == 'rmsprop':
    optimizer = RMSprop(learning_rate=learning_rate)
model.compile(optimizer=optimizer, loss='mean_squared_error')
return model
# Define the objective function
def objective(params):
    timesteps = int(params['timesteps'])
    batch_size = int(params['batch_size'])
    units_layer1 = int(params['units_layer1'])
    dropout_rate_layer1 = params['dropout_rate_layer1']
    units_layer2 = int(params['units_layer2'])
    dropout_rate_layer2 = params['dropout_rate_layer2']
    optimizer_name = params['optimizer']
    learning_rate = params['learning_rate']
    # Cross validation
    fold_no = 1
    val_losses = []
    for train_index, val_index in tscv.split(X):
        # Split data into training and validation sets
        X_train, X_val = X.iloc[train_index], X.iloc[val_index]
        y_train, y_val = y.iloc[train_index], y.iloc[val_index]
        # Scaling on training data
        feature_scaler = MinMaxScaler()
        target_scaler = MinMaxScaler()
        X_train_scaled = feature_scaler.fit_transform(X_train)
        y_train_reshaped = y_train.values.reshape(-1, 1)
        y_train_scaled = target_scaler.fit_transform(y_train_reshaped).flatten()
        # Transform validation data using training scalers
        X_val_scaled = feature_scaler.transform(X_val)
        y_val_reshaped = y_val.values.reshape(-1, 1)
        y_val_scaled = target_scaler.transform(y_val_reshaped).flatten()
        # Create sequences
        X_train_sequences, y_train_sequences = create_sequences(X_train_scaled, y_train_scaled, timesteps)
        X_val_sequences, y_val_sequences = create_sequences(X_val_scaled, y_val_scaled, timesteps)
        # Get input shape for the LSTM model
        input_shape = X_train_sequences.shape[2]
        model = create_lstm_model(timesteps, batch_size, units_layer1, dropout_rate_layer1, units_layer2,
                                  dropout_rate_layer2, optimizer_name, learning_rate, input_shape)
        # EarlyStopping
        early_stopping = EarlyStopping(monitor='val_loss', patience=5, restore_best_weights=True)
        history = model.fit(X_train_sequences, y_train_sequences, epochs=100, batch_size=batch_size, verbose=0,
                            validation_data=(X_val_sequences, y_val_sequences), callbacks=[early_stopping])
        val_loss = model.evaluate(X_val_sequences, y_val_sequences, verbose=0)

```

```

    val_losses.append(val_loss)
    fold_no += 1
    mean_val_loss = np.mean(val_losses)
    return mean_val_loss
# Parameter optimization
def optimize_lstm(trial):
    timesteps = trial.suggest_categorical('timesteps', [10, 20, 50, 100])
    batch_size = trial.suggest_int('batch_size', 16, 64, step=16)
    units_layer1 = trial.suggest_int('units_layer1', 30, 70, step=10)
    dropout_rate_layer1 = trial.suggest_float('dropout_rate_layer1', 0.1, 0.4, step=0.1)
    units_layer2 = trial.suggest_int('units_layer2', 20, 50, step=10)
    dropout_rate_layer2 = trial.suggest_float('dropout_rate_layer2', 0.1, 0.4, step=0.1)
    optimizer_name = trial.suggest_categorical('optimizer', ['adam', 'rmsprop'])
    learning_rate = trial.suggest_float('learning_rate', 1e-5, 1e-2, log=True)
    return objective({'timesteps': timesteps, 'batch_size': batch_size, 'units_layer1': units_layer1,
                    'dropout_rate_layer1': dropout_rate_layer1, 'units_layer2': units_layer2,
                    'dropout_rate_layer2': dropout_rate_layer2, 'optimizer': optimizer_name,
                    'learning_rate': learning_rate})
# Optuna sampler
sampler = optuna.samplers.TPESampler(seed=42)
study = optuna.create_study(direction='minimize', sampler=sampler)
study.optimize(optimize_lstm, n_trials=80)
# Output the best hyperparameters and value
print("Best hyperparameters: ", study.best_params)
print("Best trial value: ", study.best_value)

```

6.1.2 LSTM model training using the best hyperparameters

In the previous step, the smallest average validation loss obtained was 0.17125244965427555, corresponding to the following optimal hyperparameter combination: Timesteps: 20, batch size: 16, units on layer 1: 50, dropout rate on layer 1: 0.1, units on layer 2: 40, dropout rate on layer 2: 0.1, optimizer: Adam, and learning rate: 0.001063189574959334. Using these hyperparameters, an LSTM model was constructed and trained. The specific steps are as follows:

First, after importing all necessary libraries and setting a random seed for reproducibility, 16 features across 1950 observations were imported and divided into 90% for the training set and 10% for the validation set. The MinMaxScaler was used to scale the training set, and the scalers were saved using joblib. These scalers were then used to transform the validation data and later the final test data. The number of epochs was set to 100, and ModelCheckpoint was used to save the best model. After training

the model, the training loss over epochs was plotted, and the MSE, RMSE, MAE, MAPE and R^2 of both the training set and the validation set were calculated. The concrete model training process is detailed in Code 2.

Code 2. LSTM model training code

```
!pip install joblib
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from sklearn.preprocessing import MinMaxScaler
from keras.models import Sequential
from keras.layers import LSTM, Dense, Dropout, Input
from keras.callbacks import EarlyStopping, ModelCheckpoint
from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error, mean_absolute_error, mean_absolute_percentage_error,
r2_score
from keras.optimizers import Adam, RMSprop
import random
import os
import tensorflow as tf
from joblib import dump
# Random seed
np.random.seed(42)
random.seed(42)
tf.random.set_seed(42)
os.environ['PYTHONHASHSEED'] = str(42)
# ModelCheckpoint
checkpoint = ModelCheckpoint('best_model_LSTM.keras', monitor='val_loss', save_best_only=True, mode='min',
verbose=0)
# Load data
data = pd.read_csv('Train data.csv')
# Date column is datetime and set as index
data['Date'] = pd.to_datetime(data['Date'])
data.set_index('Date', inplace=True)
# Select features and target
features = data[['Open', 'High', 'Low', 'Close', 'EMA_10', 'EMA_20', 'SMA_50', 'SMA_100', 'Bollinger_Upper',
'Bollinger_Lower', 'Miners Revenue', 'Hash Rate', 'Difficulty', 'Gold', 'S&P 500', 'NASDAQ']]
target = data['Close']
# Create train and validation datasets (90% training, 10% validation)
train_size = int(len(features) * 0.9)
train_features, val_features = features[:train_size], features[train_size:]
train_target, val_target = target[:train_size], target[train_size:]
# Initialize scalers
scaler_features = MinMaxScaler()
```

```

scaler_target = MinMaxScaler()
# Fit scalers on training data
scaled_train_features = scaler_features.fit_transform(train_features)
scaled_train_target = scaler_target.fit_transform(train_target.values.reshape(-1, 1))
# Use the same scalers to transform validation data
scaled_val_features = scaler_features.transform(val_features)
scaled_val_target = scaler_target.transform(val_target.values.reshape(-1, 1))
# Set time step
time_step = 20
# Create dataset for LSTM
def create_dataset(features, target, time_step):
    X, y = [], []
    for i in range(len(features) - time_step):
        X.append(features[i:(i + time_step), :])
        y.append(target[i + time_step])
    return np.array(X), np.array(y)
X_train, y_train = create_dataset(scaled_train_features, scaled_train_target, time_step)
X_val, y_val = create_dataset(scaled_val_features, scaled_val_target, time_step)
# Reshape input to be [samples, time steps, features]
X_train = X_train.reshape(X_train.shape[0], X_train.shape[1], X_train.shape[2])
X_val = X_val.reshape(X_val.shape[0], X_val.shape[1], X_val.shape[2])
# Build and compile LSTM model
model = Sequential()
model.add(Input(shape=(X_train.shape[1], X_train.shape[2])))
model.add(LSTM(50, return_sequences=True))
model.add(Dropout(0.1))
model.add(LSTM(40, return_sequences=False))
model.add(Dropout(0.1))
model.add(Dense(1))
optimizer = Adam(learning_rate=0.001063189574959334)
model.compile(optimizer=optimizer, loss='mean_squared_error')
# Train model
history = model.fit(X_train, y_train, epochs=100, batch_size=16, validation_data=(X_val, y_val), verbose=0,
callbacks=[checkpoint])
# Predict
train_predict = model.predict(X_train)
val_predict = model.predict(X_val)
# Inverse transform predictions and actual values
train_predict_inverse = scaler_target.inverse_transform(train_predict)
val_predict_inverse = scaler_target.inverse_transform(val_predict)
y_train_inverse = scaler_target.inverse_transform(y_train.reshape(-1, 1))
y_val_inverse = scaler_target.inverse_transform(y_val.reshape(-1, 1))
# Calculate metrics
train_mse = mean_squared_error(y_train_inverse, train_predict_inverse)

```

```

val_mse = mean_squared_error(y_val_inverse, val_predict_inverse)
train_rmse = np.sqrt(train_mse)
val_rmse = np.sqrt(val_mse)
train_mae = mean_absolute_error(y_train_inverse, train_predict_inverse)
val_mae = mean_absolute_error(y_val_inverse, val_predict_inverse)
train_mape = mean_absolute_percentage_error(y_train_inverse, train_predict_inverse) * 100
val_mape = mean_absolute_percentage_error(y_val_inverse, val_predict_inverse) * 100
train_r2 = r2_score(y_train_inverse, train_predict_inverse)
val_r2 = r2_score(y_val_inverse, val_predict_inverse)
# Print metrics
print(f'Train MSE: {train_mse:.4f}')
print(f'Validation MSE: {val_mse:.4f}')
print(f'Train RMSE: {train_rmse:.4f}')
print(f'Validation RMSE: {val_rmse:.4f}')
print(f'Train MAE: {train_mae:.4f}')
print(f'Validation MAE: {val_mae:.4f}')
print(f'Train MAPE: {train_mape:.4f}%')
print(f'Validation MAPE: {val_mape:.4f}%')
print(f'Train R-squared: {train_r2:.4f}')
print(f'Validation R-squared: {val_r2:.4f}')
# Plot training loss over epochs
plt.figure(figsize=(14, 5))
plt.plot(history.history['loss'], label='Train Loss')
plt.plot(history.history['val_loss'], label='Validation Loss')
plt.title('LSTM Model Loss')
plt.xlabel('Epoch')
plt.ylabel('Loss')
plt.legend()
plt.show()
# Check best epoch
best_epoch = np.argmin(history.history['val_loss']) + 1
print(f'Best model was saved at epoch: {best_epoch}')
# Save scalers
dump(scaler_features, 'scaler_features_LSTM.joblib')
dump(scaler_target, 'scaler_target_LSTM.joblib')

```

6.1.3 LSTM model testing using the best model

The best model was saved at epoch 91. Using the best model and scalers saved from the above step, the performance of the optimal LSTM model was tested on the final 16 features across 492 observations, and a visualization of the actual vs. predicted Bitcoin prices was plotted. The testing process is detailed in Code 3.

Code 3. LSTM model testing code

```
!pip install joblib
from tensorflow.keras.models import load_model
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.preprocessing import MinMaxScaler
from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error, mean_absolute_error, r2_score
from joblib import dump, load

# Load data
test_data = pd.read_csv('Final test data.csv')
# Set Date as index
test_data['Date'] = pd.to_datetime(test_data['Date'])
test_data.set_index('Date', inplace=True)
# Features and target
X_test = test_data[['Open', 'High', 'Low', 'Close', 'EMA_10', 'EMA_20', 'SMA_50', 'SMA_100', 'Bollinger_Upper',
                    'Bollinger_Lower', 'Miners Revenue', 'Hash Rate', 'Difficulty', 'Gold', 'S&P 500', 'NASDAQ']]
y_test = test_data['Close']
# Load scalers
scaler_features = load('scaler_features_LSTM.joblib')
scaler_target = load('scaler_target_LSTM.joblib')
# Scale features
scaled_X_test = scaler_features.transform(X_test)
scaled_y_test = scaler_target.transform(y_test.values.reshape(-1, 1))
# Create sequences for LSTM
timesteps = 20
def create_sequences(X, y, timesteps):
    X_sequences = []
    y_sequences = []
    for i in range(len(X) - timesteps):
        X_sequences.append(X[i:i + timesteps])
        y_sequences.append(y[i + timesteps])
    return np.array(X_sequences), np.array(y_sequences)
X_test_sequences, y_test_sequences = create_sequences(scaled_X_test, scaled_y_test, timesteps)
# Load best model
best_model = load_model('best_model_LSTM.keras')
# Print model summary
best_model.summary()
# Evaluate model on test data
test_loss = best_model.evaluate(X_test_sequences, y_test_sequences, verbose=1)
print(f'Test Loss: {test_loss:.4f}')
# Make predictions
y_pred = best_model.predict(X_test_sequences)
# Inverse transform predictions and actual values
```

```

y_pred_rescaled = scaler_target.inverse_transform(y_pred)
y_test_rescaled = scaler_target.inverse_transform(y_test_sequences)
# Plot actual vs predicted values
plt.figure(figsize=(14, 7))
plt.plot(y_test_rescaled, label='Actual Values', color='blue')
plt.plot(y_pred_rescaled, label='Predicted Values', linestyle='--', color='red')
plt.title('Actual vs Predicted Values - LSTM')
plt.xlabel('Sample Index')
plt.ylabel('Value')
plt.legend()
plt.show()
# Calculate performance metrics
mse = mean_squared_error(y_test_rescaled, y_pred_rescaled)
rmse = np.sqrt(mse)
mae = mean_absolute_error(y_test_rescaled, y_pred_rescaled)
mape = np.mean(np.abs((y_test_rescaled - y_pred_rescaled) / y_test_rescaled)) * 100
r2 = r2_score(y_test_rescaled, y_pred_rescaled)
print(f'MSE: {mse:.4f}')
print(f'RMSE: {rmse:.4f}')
print(f'MAE: {mae:.4f}')
print(f'MAPE: {mape:.4f}%')
print(f'R2: {r2:.4f}')

```

6.1.4 Train and test the other models using LSTM's best hyperparameters

After completing all the steps for the LSTM model, from hyperparameters optimization to model testing, the same hyperparameter combination - i.e., the optimal hyperparameters from the LSTM model obtained in section 6.1.1 - was used to construct GRU, LSTM-GRU and GRU-LSTM models following the same methods and steps. Their performance and stability were then compared.

6.2 GRU, LSTM-GRU and GRU-LSTM model training

Using the same method and keeping all settings unchanged, the optimal hyperparameter combinations for the GRU, LSTM-GRU and GRU-LSTM models were determined. Thus, this study identified an optimal hyperparameter combination for each of the four models respectively. Each of these optimal hyperparameter combinations was then used to construct all the four models, and the performances of these models were compared. In terms of the code, everything remained the same except for (partially) replacing LSTM with GRU.

7. Results

7.1 Best hyperparameter combinations

The results of the best hyperparameter combinations are presented below in Table 4. The trial value was calculated as the average MSE of the validation sets across all folds after cross-validation. The trial value for the GRU model is 0.03766969, significantly lower than those of the other three models, indicating that the GRU model using its optimal hyperparameter combination found within the same hyperparameter search space resulted in far superior performance compared to the other models under their respective optimal hyperparameter combinations. However, this does not necessarily imply that training the GRU model with this optimal hyperparameter combination will result in strong generalization ability. The pros and cons of using the average MSE of the validation sets across all folds as an evaluation metric are discussed in a subsequent section. Therefore, it is crucial to consider the research steps after the hyperparameter optimization and the other evaluation metrics in conjunction.

Table 4. Best hyperparameter combinations derived from different models

	LSTM	GRU	LSTM-GRU	GRU-LSTM
Timesteps	20	10	50	20
Batch size	16	16	16	64
Units layer 1	50	70	50	60
Dropout rate layer 1	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.3
Units layer 2	40	40	50	40
Dropout rate layer 2	0.1	0.4	0.4	0.2
Optimizer	Adam	RMSprop	Adam	RMSprop
Learning rate	0.00106319	0.00094741	0.00172495	0.00062248
Trial value	0.17125245	0.03766969	0.12843572	0.19759531

7.2 LSTM model training, testing and comparison with the other models

As previously mentioned, this study utilized an automated tuning method to identify the optimal hyperparameter combination for the LSTM model within a specified range. The best hyperparameter combination identified is as follows: Timesteps: 20, batch size: 16, units in layer 1: 50, dropout rate in layer 1: 0.1, units in layer 2: 40, dropout rate in layer 2: 0.1, optimizer: Adam, and learning rate: 0.001063189574959334. All models were run using this hyperparameter combination. The experiment results are summarized in Table 5.

The results indicate that on the training set, the GRU model has the lowest MSE (1,284,551.6111), demonstrating the best performance. The GRU-LSTM hybrid model follows closely with a slightly higher MSE (1,285,751.9008), while the LSTM-GRU model has the highest MSE, indicating that its fitting effect on the training set is relatively poor. On the validation set, the GRU-LSTM model achieves the lowest MSE (450,395.5640), showing the most accurate performance on the validation set. The GRU model comes next with an MSE of 469,726.8617, while the LSTM model performs the worst with an MSE of 667,181.0690. The test set results reveal that the GRU model has the best generalization ability on new data, with the lowest MSE (7,017,228.5877), significantly outperforming the other three models.

In terms of RMSE, the GRU model (1133.3806 for training and 685.3662 for validation) and the GRU-LSTM model (1133.9100 for training and 671.1152 for validation) both have lower RMSEs compared to the LSTM (1227.5977 for training and 816.8115 for validation) and LSTM-GRU (1286.2104 for training and 762.1151 for validation), indicating that the GRU and GRU-LSTM models have smaller prediction errors on these two datasets. On the test set, the GRU model's RMSE (2649.0052) is significantly lower than those of the other three models, demonstrating the best performance.

The GRU model has the lowest MAE in both the training set (748.2332) and the test set (1769.2855), further confirming its smaller prediction errors and higher model accuracy. In the validation set, the MAE of the GRU model (493.2407) is slightly higher than the lowest MAE achieved by the GRU-LSTM model (470.2371).

The LSTM model has the lowest MAPE on the training set (4.5762%), followed by the GRU model (4.6498%). On the validation set, the GRU-LSTM model has the lowest MAPE (2.3011%), followed again by the GRU model (2.4288%). The GRU model performs the best on the test set, with a MAPE of 3.2357%, significantly lower than those of the other three models.

In terms of explanatory power, all four models exhibit good fitting performance on the training set, with the lowest R-squared being 0.9945 for the LSTM-GRU model and the highest being 0.9958 for both the GRU and GRU-LSTM models. On the validation set, the GRU-LSTM model has the highest R-squared (0.9581), followed by the GRU

model (0.9563). The differences become more pronounced on the test set, where the GRU model's R-squared (0.9738) is significantly higher than those of the other three models, indicating that the GRU model has the strongest explanatory power on the test data.

The GRU model reached its optimal state at the 77th epoch, indicating that it converges relatively quickly. In contrast, the LSTM, LSTM-GRU, and GRU-LSTM models saved their best models at the 91st, 86th, and 100th epochs, respectively. The GRU model's test loss (0.0017) is also significantly lower than those of the other three models, demonstrating its overall superior performance on the test data.

Through a comprehensive analysis of the above metrics, the GRU model demonstrates outstanding performance across the training, validation and test sets, particularly in terms of generalization ability and prediction accuracy on the test set, where it significantly outperforms the other models. Although the GRU-LSTM model slightly outperforms on the validation set, its performance on test data falls short compared to the GRU model. The performances of the LSTM model and the LSTM-GRU model are relatively poor.

Table 5. Model performance comparison

		LSTM	GRU	LSTM-GRU	GRU-LSTM
MSE	Train	1506996.0594	1284551.6111	1654337.2857	1285751.9008
	Validation	667181.0690	469726.8617	580819.3535	450395.5640
	Test	29883502.8067	7017228.5877	22113402.1710	23000210.6742
RMSE	Train	1227.5977	1133.3806	1286.2104	1133.9100
	Validation	816.8115	685.3662	762.1151	671.1152
	Test	5466.5805	2649.0052	4702.4889	4795.8535
MAE	Train	787.0650	748.2332	899.7001	783.1985
	Validation	556.3831	493.2407	531.5356	470.2371
	Test	4178.1790	1769.2855	3519.3921	3311.1108
MAPE	Train	4.5762%	4.6498%	5.8341%	5.2367%
	Validation	2.6546%	2.4288%	2.6081%	2.3011%
	Test	8.0526%	3.2357%	6.6360%	5.8557%
R-squared	Train	0.9950	0.9958	0.9945	0.9958
	Validation	0.9379	0.9563	0.9459	0.9581
	Test	0.8886	0.9738	0.9175	0.9142
Best model saved at epoch		91	77	86	100
Test loss		0.0072	0.0017	0.0053	0.0056

All models run with the best hyperparameters of LSTM. Timesteps: 20, batch size: 16, units layer 1: 50, dropout rate layer 1: 0.1, units layer 2: 40, dropout rate layer 2: 0.1, optimizer: Adam, learning rate: 0.001063189574959334.

Figure 5 shows the model loss for each model. The LSTM's training loss decreases rapidly within the first few epochs, dropping below 0.002 around the 5th epoch and then stabilizing with a slow decline. This indicates that the model learns most of the patterns early on. The validation loss also shows a slow declining trend with some fluctuations. The other three models exhibit similar patterns: their training losses decrease rapidly and then stabilize. The validation loss curves for these models also show a relatively smooth downward trend. All models are able to quickly learn patterns in the data and converge rapidly in the early stages. Compared to LSTM, the GRU, LSTM-GRU, and GRU-LSTM models show less fluctuation in their validation loss curves, suggesting that the GRU model performs more stably than the LSTM model and combining GRU with LSTM can also enhance the stability of the latter.

Figure 5. Model loss comparison

Figure 6 provides a visual comparison of the actual Bitcoin prices and the predicted prices from each model on the test set. It is evident that the GRU model outperforms the other models.

Figure 6. Test results comparison

7.3 GRU model training, testing and comparison with the other models

This part shows the model performances based on the best hyperparameter combination for the GRU model. The best hyperparameter combination identified is as follows: Timesteps: 10, batch size: 16, units in layer 1: 70, dropout rate in layer 1: 0.2, units in layer 2: 40, dropout rate in layer 2: 0.4, optimizer: RMSprop, and learning rate: 0.0009474097135596231. All models were run using this hyperparameter combination. The experiment results are summarized in Table 6.

In terms of MSE, the LSTM model has the lowest values for both the training and validation sets, with MSEs of 1,692,163.2601 and 703,051.6721, respectively. The GRU model follows, with MSEs of 1,824,573.1405 for the training set and 991,845.1726 for the validation set. The MSEs for the LSTM-GRU and GRU-LSTM models are noticeably higher, especially with GRU-LSTM reaching 4,361,392.7757 on the training set. On the test set, the GRU model again performs the best, with an MSE of 5,109,039.0738, which is significantly lower than those of the other three models.

Similar to MSE, the LSTM model has the lowest RMSE values for both the training and validation sets, with RMSEs of 1,300.8318 and 838.4818, respectively. The GRU model is next, with RMSEs of 1,350.7676 for the training set and 995.9142 for the validation set. On the test set, the GRU model again performs the best, with an RMSE of 2,260.3184, which is significantly lower than those of the other three models.

The LSTM model also outperforms the GRU model in terms of MAE on both the training set (878.6018) and the validation set (544.0491). The MAE for the GRU model is 978.2787 on the training set and 829.0563 on the validation set. However, on the test set, the GRU's MAE (1,525.9388) is still significantly lower than those of the other three models.

The same trend is observed for MAPE and R^2 . The LSTM model performs slightly better than the GRU model on both the training and validation sets. However, on the test set, the GRU model significantly outperforms the other models, with an MAPE of 2.9183% and an R^2 of 0.9809. The performances of the two hybrid models are relatively poor.

The GRU model reached its best performance at the 88th epoch, indicating that it converges faster compared to the other three models. In contrast, the LSTM, LSTM-GRU, and GRU-LSTM models saved their best models at the 100th, 94th, and 94th epochs, respectively. The GRU model's test loss (0.0012) is also significantly lower than those of the other three models, demonstrating its superior overall performance on the test data.

Based on the comprehensive analysis of the various metrics, the GRU model performs the best, particularly in terms of generalization capability and prediction accuracy on the test set, significantly outperforming the other models. Although the LSTM model slightly excels on the training and validation sets, its performance on the test data is inferior to that of the GRU model. The two hybrid models, on the other hand, show relatively poor performance.

Table 6. Model performance comparison

		LSTM	GRU	LSTM-GRU	GRU-LSTM
MSE	Train	1692163.2601	1824573.1405	2687829.5240	4361392.7757
	Validation	703051.6721	991845.1726	1459585.3694	4186086.2093
	Test	33263134.7038	5109039.0738	37840643.9814	32021724.7286
RMSE	Train	1300.8318	1350.7676	1639.4601	2088.3948
	Validation	838.4818	995.9142	1208.1330	2045.9927
	Test	5767.4201	2260.3184	6151.4749	5658.7741
MAE	Train	878.6018	978.2787	1279.3394	1602.7438
	Validation	544.0491	829.0563	1053.3613	1926.0078
	Test	4130.6908	1525.9388	4465.5996	4016.6302
MAPE	Train	5.6764%	6.8934%	9.7983%	10.6368%
	Validation	2.6377%	4.1448%	5.3730%	9.7821%
	Test	7.5953%	2.9183%	8.2614%	7.2968%
R-squared	Train	0.9944	0.9940	0.9911	0.9855
	Validation	0.9312	0.9030	0.8572	0.5904
	Test	0.8754	0.9809	0.8582	0.8800
Best model saved at epoch		100	88	94	94
Test loss		0.0080	0.0012	0.0091	0.0077

All models run with the best hyperparameters of GRU. Timesteps: 10, batch size: 16, units layer 1: 70, dropout rate layer 1: 0.2, units layer 2: 40, dropout rate layer 2: 0.4, optimizer: RMSprop, learning rate: 0.0009474097135596231.

Figure 7 presents the model loss for each model. The LSTM model's training loss decreases rapidly below 0.004 within the first few epochs and then gradually stabilizes, with the final training loss value remaining slightly above 0.002. The validation loss fluctuates significantly in the early stages, especially with noticeable variations in the first 20 epochs. Although these fluctuations decrease over time, the validation loss remains relatively variable overall. While the general trend is downward, it is not as smooth as the training loss, indicating weaker stability of the model on the validation set. The LSTM-GRU and GRU-LSTM models show similar patterns: their training loss curves converge quickly, but their validation loss curves exhibit evident fluctuations. The GRU model's training loss decreases rapidly and gradually stabilizes around 0.0025, showing good stability in its curve. Although the GRU's validation loss curve performs better than that of the LSTM, it still exhibits noticeable fluctuations, especially in the initial epochs. Overall, the GRU's validation loss decreases gradually, with reduced but still significant volatility, indicating some instability.

In summary, all models display considerable fluctuations in validation loss, particularly

in the early epochs. Although the GRU shows less fluctuation compared to the other three models, the overall generalization capability of this group of models on the validation set is less stable compared to the previous group. Therefore, there is a subsequent part focusing on a comparative analysis of the validation loss for the four GRU models under different hyperparameter combinations.

Figure 7. Model loss comparison

Figure 8 provides a visual comparison of the actual Bitcoin prices and the predicted prices from each model in the test set. It is evident that the GRU model still outperforms the other models. However, considering that all models in this group exhibit high instability on the validation set, even though the GRU model in this group (MSE: 5,109,039.0738, RMSE: 2,260.3184, MAE: 1,525.9388, MAPE: 2.9183%, R²: 0.9809) performs better across all metrics on the test set compared to the best-performing GRU model from the previous group (MSE: 7,017,228.5877, RMSE: 2,649.0052, MAE: 1,769.2855, MAPE: 3.2357%, R²: 0.9738), the former's stability is still questionable.

Figure 8. Test results comparison

7.4 LSTM-GRU hybrid model training, testing and comparison with the other models

This part shows the model performances based on the best hyperparameter combination for the LSTM-GRU model. The best hyperparameter combination identified is as follows: Timesteps: 50, batch size: 16, units in layer 1: 50, dropout rate in layer 1: 0.4, units in layer 2: 50, dropout rate in layer 2: 0.4, optimizer: Adam, and learning rate: 0.0017249472838219754. All models were run using this hyperparameter combination. The experiment results are summarized in Table 7.

On the training set, the LSTM model achieves the lowest MSE (1,409,937.0518), performing the best, followed by the GRU-LSTM model (1,457,340.1307). The GRU model has the highest MSE (2,348,380.2395), indicating the largest prediction error on the training data. However, on the validation set, the GRU's performance improves significantly, with an MSE (1,076,570.5262) only slightly higher than the lowest MSE (925,203.8952) of the GRU-LSTM model. The GRU model performs even better on the test set, where its MSE (18,388,510.8147) is much lower than those of the other models. In contrast, the GRU-LSTM model has the highest MSE (51,135,935.9213), performing the worst on the test set.

The RMSE follows a similar pattern. The GRU-LSTM model performs well on the training set (1,207.2034) and validation set (961.8752) but performs the worst on the test set (7,150.9395). On the other hand, the GRU model performs the worst on the training set (1,532.4426), improves to the second place on the validation set with an RMSE of 1,037.5792, and ultimately ranks the first on the test set with an RMSE of 4,288.1827.

MAE, MAPE, and R^2 also reflect the same pattern. The GRU model performs the worst on the training set, with an MAE of 1,043.3866, an MAPE of 7.4797%, and an R^2 of 0.9924. However, on the validation set, the GRU model quickly surpasses the LSTM and LSTM-GRU models, achieving an MAE of 729.9384, an MAPE of 3.5194%, and an R^2 of 0.9160. Finally, the GRU model significantly outperforms the other three models on the test set, with an MAE of 2,933.1863, an MAPE of 5.2803%, and an R^2 of 0.9314.

The GRU model has the fastest convergence, with the best model saved at the 48th epoch. In contrast, the LSTM model requires more epochs to reach its optimal state, with the best model saved at the 99th epoch. The hybrid models are between these two, with the LSTM-GRU model saved at the 62nd epoch and the GRU-LSTM model at the 87th epoch. The GRU model's test loss is 0.0044, significantly lower than those of the other three models, indicating the best test performance. Consistent with the experiment results of the previous groups, the GRU model remains the most superior on the test set.

Table 7. Model performance comparison

		LSTM	GRU	LSTM-GRU	GRU-LSTM
MSE	Train	1409937.0518	2348380.2395	1551769.2622	1457340.1307
	Validation	1619798.0105	1076570.5262	2656497.8444	925203.8952
	Test	31341361.3331	18388510.8147	31786694.4493	51135935.9213
RMSE	Train	1187.4077	1532.4426	1245.7003	1207.2034
	Validation	1272.7129	1037.5792	1629.8766	961.8752
	Test	5598.3356	4288.1827	5637.9690	7150.9395
MAE	Train	728.7765	1043.3866	787.1983	778.7627
	Validation	1014.9188	729.9384	1345.5361	727.3285
	Test	4154.8329	2933.1863	4020.3164	4853.1462
MAPE	Train	3.8070%	7.4797%	4.6710%	4.5249%
	Validation	4.9093%	3.5194%	6.3807%	3.6150%
	Test	7.6859%	5.2803%	7.2379%	8.2118%

	Train	0.9954	0.9924	0.9950	0.9953
R-squared	Validation	0.8736	0.9160	0.7927	0.9278
	Test	0.8831	0.9314	0.8814	0.8093
	Best model saved at epoch	99	48	62	87
	Test loss	0.0076	0.0044	0.0077	0.0124

All models run with the best hyperparameters of LSTM-GRU. Timesteps: 50, batch size: 16, units layer 1: 50, dropout rate layer 1: 0.4, units layer 2: 50, dropout rate layer 2: 0.4, optimizer: Adam, learning rate: 0.0017249472838219754.

Figure 9 presents the model loss for each model. The training loss of the LSTM model drops rapidly during the first few epochs and then stabilizes at around 0.002. The curve is overall smooth, indicating good convergence on the training set. The validation loss also decreases quickly but exhibits significant fluctuations, especially during the first 20 epochs. Although the validation loss remains at a low level in the subsequent epochs, it continues to show some degree of variability.

The training loss of the GRU model decreases rapidly and stabilizes after about the 10th epoch, ultimately remaining below 0.0025. Compared to the LSTM model, GRU's validation loss curve is smoother, with some fluctuations in the early stages but generally lower and gradually stabilizing.

The model losses of the two hybrid models generally fall between those of the single LSTM and GRU models. Overall, the training losses of all four models demonstrate rapid convergence, while the validation losses exhibit some degree of fluctuation across all models. In comparison, the GRU model's validation loss curve is the smoothest, indicating a relatively strong generalization ability.

Figure 9. Model loss comparison

Figure 10 offers a visual comparison between the actual Bitcoin prices and the predicted prices from each model on the test set. It is evident that the GRU model still outperforms the other models. However, compared to the GRU models in the previous two groups, this GRU model's performance is weaker.

Figure 10. Test results comparison

7.5 GRU-LSTM hybrid model training, testing and comparison with the other models

This part shows the model performances based on the best hyperparameter combination for the GRU model. The best hyperparameter combination identified is as follows: Timesteps: 20, batch size: 64, units in layer 1: 60, dropout rate in layer 1: 0.3, units in layer 2: 40, dropout rate in layer 2: 0.2, optimizer: RMSprop, and learning rate: 0.0006224805845129522. All models were run using this hyperparameter combination. The experiment results are summarized in Table 8.

Comparing the MSE and RMSE of each model reveals that the LSTM has the lowest MSE and RMSE on the training set (8,990,954.7428 and 2,998.4921, respectively) and on the validation set (5,300,648.1037 and 2,302.3136, respectively). However, on the test set, the GRU model's MSE and RMSE are significantly lower than those of the other three models, at 3,920,068.8000 and 1,979.9164, respectively.

The same pattern is observed with MAE and MAPE. The LSTM model has the lowest MAE (1,862.1440 and 2,053.7320) and MAPE (7.3759% and 9.9615%) on the training and validation sets, respectively, showing the best performance. However, this performance does not carry over to the test set. On the test set, the GRU model outperforms the other three models with an MAE of 1,385.3016 and an MAPE of 2.9288%.

It is worth noting that the R^2 metric fluctuates significantly on all of the models. On the training set, the R^2 values for LSTM, GRU, LSTM-GRU, and GRU-LSTM are 0.9703, 0.9580, 0.9549, and 0.9628, respectively. However, on the validation set, these values drop dramatically to 0.5066, 0.1606, 0.0762, and 0.1044, showing a large gap from the training set. Interestingly, the performances improve again on the test set, with R^2 values of 0.9149, 0.9854, 0.9159, and 0.8845, respectively. The GRU model stands out with an R^2 of 0.9854, the highest among all 16 models across the four groups.

The best GRU model was saved at the 80th epoch, making it the most efficient. The least efficient is the LSTM model, with its best model saved at the 97th epoch. The two hybrid models perform between the two single models. The GRU's test loss is 0.0009, significantly lower than those of the other three models, and the lowest among all 16 models across the four groups.

Overall, the GRU once again outperforms the other three models, especially considering its outstanding performance on the test set. This GRU model's performance on the test set is even the best among all 16 models across the four groups. However, considering its inconsistent performance on the training and validation sets, particularly on the validation set, even though the GRU model achieves very good results, its true performance may be significantly compromised.

Table 8. Model performance comparison

		LSTM	GRU	LSTM-GRU	GRU-LSTM
MSE	Train	8990954.7428	12739903.1030	13669131.1513	11290425.8921
	Validation	5300648.1037	9017385.7926	9924048.1544	9621364.2772
	Test	22823651.8959	3920068.8000	22544430.9805	30960850.3225
RMSE	Train	2998.4921	3569.3001	3697.1788	3360.1229
	Validation	2302.3136	3002.8962	3150.2457	3101.8324
	Test	4777.4106	1979.9164	4748.0976	5564.2475
MAE	Train	1862.1440	2336.2416	2405.5021	2167.9554
	Validation	2053.7320	2855.5560	2976.9066	2902.5687
	Test	3237.7183	1385.3016	3261.7298	3934.7035
MAPE	Train	7.3759%	9.2420%	9.4333%	8.6571%
	Validation	9.9615%	13.9919%	14.5290%	14.0623%
	Test	5.8399%	2.9288%	5.8572%	7.1054%
R-squared	Train	0.9703	0.9580	0.9549	0.9628
	Validation	0.5066	0.1606	0.0762	0.1044
	Test	0.9149	0.9854	0.9159	0.8845
Best model saved at epoch		97	80	90	96
Test loss		0.0055	0.0009	0.0055	0.0075

All models run with the best hyperparameters of GRU-LSTM. Timesteps: 20, batch size: 64, units layer 1: 60, dropout rate layer 1: 0.3, units layer 2: 40, dropout rate layer 2: 0.2, optimizer: RMSprop, learning rate: 0.0006224805845129522.

Figure 11 presents the model loss for each model. The training loss of the LSTM model quickly decreases in the early stages and gradually stabilizes around 0.002. The validation loss shows significant fluctuations, though the curve overall tends to stabilize as it declines. The GRU model exhibits a similar pattern, but its validation loss curve appears to fluctuate more than that of the LSTM. The model loss curves of the two hybrid models, LSTM-GRU and GRU-LSTM, seem smoother compared to the two single models. However, considering the scale of the vertical axis, their fluctuations are actually quite significant, especially for the LSTM-GRU model, whose validation loss curve starts very high before dropping rapidly. Overall, similar to the second group, all

models in this group suffer from significant fluctuations in the validation loss curves, leading to unstable generalization performance on the validation set.

Figure 11. Model loss comparison

Figure 12 provides a visual comparison between the actual Bitcoin prices and the predicted prices from each model on the test set. The GRU model's predictions are not only the closest to the actual prices among the four models but also the most closely aligned with the actual price trends across all 16 models in the four groups. However, considering its inconsistent performance, the excellent results of this GRU model may be unreliable.

Figure 12. Test results comparison

7.6 Comparative analysis of the GRU models

Since the GRU model outperforms the other three models across all four groups, this part focuses on a comparative analysis of the GRU models. Table 9 compiles the results of various metrics for all the GRU models.

The GRU model created using the optimal hyperparameters from the LSTM performs the best on the training and validation sets. It achieves the best results across all metrics. Its MSE, RMSE, MAE, MAPE, and R² are 1,284,551.6111 (training set) and 469,726.8617 (validation set), 1,133.3806 (training set) and 685.3662 (validation set), 748.2332 (training set) and 493.2407 (validation set), 4.6498% (training set) and 2.4288% (validation set), and 0.9958 (training set) and 0.9563 (validation set), respectively.

On the test set, the best performance can be seen on the GRU model created using the optimal hyperparameter combination from GRU-LSTM and the GRU model created using the optimal hyperparameter combination from GRU. Their MSEs on the test set are 3,920,068.8000 and 5,109,039.0738, their RMSEs are 1,979.9164 and 2,260.3184, their MAEs are 1,385.3016 and 1,525.9388, their MAPEs are 2.9288% and 2.9183%, and their R² values are 0.9854 and 0.9809, respectively. However, considering their

poor performances on the training set and instability on the validation set, even though they perform well on the test set, they may struggle to be considered the best models. The GRU model created using the optimal hyperparameters from LSTM-GRU does not perform well across the various metrics.

Table 9. Performance comparison for GRU models

		GRU (LSTM)	GRU (GRU)	GRU (LSTM-GRU)	GRU (GRU-LSTM)
MSE	Train	1284551.6111	1824573.1405	2348380.2395	12739903.1030
	Validation	469726.8617	991845.1726	1076570.5262	9017385.7926
	Test	7017228.5877	5109039.0738	18388510.8147	3920068.8000
RMSE	Train	1133.3806	1350.7676	1532.4426	3569.3001
	Validation	685.3662	995.9142	1037.5792	3002.8962
	Test	2649.0052	2260.3184	4288.1827	1979.9164
MAE	Train	748.2332	978.2787	1043.3866	2336.2416
	Validation	493.2407	829.0563	729.9384	2855.5560
	Test	1769.2855	1525.9388	2933.1863	1385.3016
MAPE	Train	4.6498%	6.8934%	7.4797%	9.2420%
	Validation	2.4288%	4.1448%	3.5194%	13.9919%
	Test	3.2357%	2.9183%	5.2803%	2.9288%
R-squared	Train	0.9958	0.9940	0.9924	0.9580
	Validation	0.9563	0.9030	0.9160	0.1606
	Test	0.9738	0.9809	0.9314	0.9854
Best model saved at epoch		77	88	48	80
Test loss		0.0017	0.0012	0.0044	0.0009

Due to the issue of performance fluctuations, Table 10 provides a detailed analysis of the validation loss for the four GRU models. Figure 13 is a visualization of the validation loss fluctuations. It can be observed that the GRU model created using the optimal hyperparameters from LSTM shows the most stable performance, with the lowest average validation loss and the smallest fluctuation. The mean validation loss is 0.0002, the standard deviation of validation loss is 0.0002, the range of validation loss is 0.0011, and the relative standard deviation of validation loss is 0.7799, all lower than those of the other three GRU models. The GRU model created using the optimal hyperparameters from LSTM-GRU follows closely behind, although its validation loss is slightly higher, its overall stability is relatively good. In contrast, the GRU models created using the optimal hyperparameters from GRU and GRU-LSTM exhibit larger fluctuations, indicating inconsistent performance across different epochs and unstable

generalization ability.

Table 10. Validation loss comparison for GRU models

	GRU (LSTM)	GRU (GRU)	GRU (LSTM-GRU)	GRU (GRU-LSTM)
Mean validation loss	0.0002	0.0014	0.0006	0.0017
Standard deviation of validation loss	0.0002	0.0018	0.0004	0.0020
Range of validation loss	0.0011	0.0107	0.0020	0.0128
Relative standard deviation of validation loss	0.7799	1.2992	0.7937	1.1778

Figure 13. Visualization of validation loss fluctuations for GRU models

Therefore, considering both the performance metrics and the stability indicators, it is evident that the GRU model created using the best hyperparameters from LSTM has strong and stable performance, making it the best model in this study.

8. Conclusion

Looking at Bitcoin's brief history, despite its ups and downs, the upward trend and the mainstream adoption are very apparent. While it may have been reasonable in the early days to be skeptical about Bitcoin and think it might eventually fade away, it now seems sensible to seriously consider its function and value. Due to Bitcoin's significant price volatility and the resulting potential for substantial profitability, many researchers and investors have delved into its price mechanisms and have sought to improve the accuracy of Bitcoin price predictions using various methods. In recent years, with the surge in AI, people have naturally been eager to apply machine learning and deep learning to analyze Bitcoin and enhance the accuracy of its price predictions.

This study aims to predict Bitcoin prices using deep learning models. After reviewing relevant academic research, the focus was placed on LSTM and GRU models, as well as their hybrid models, LSTM-GRU and GRU-LSTM. 16 features highly correlated with Bitcoin prices were selected through correlation analysis and fed into these deep learning models. During the model training process, automated hyperparameter tuning was employed to efficiently and comprehensively search for the optimal hyperparameter combinations for the models. All the four models were then trained using the same optimal hyperparameter combination identified for each model, allowing for performance comparison of all models under identical conditions. The study found that the GRU model outperformed not only the other single model LSTM but also the two hybrid models LSTM-GRU and GRU-LSTM, demonstrating strong performance in predicting Bitcoin prices.

There are many promising directions for future research, such as exploring other cryptocurrencies besides Bitcoin, investigating the application of other deep learning models like Transformers in cryptocurrencies and other financial products, and exploring the use of different tools related to deep learning models.

9. Contributions and limitations of this study

9.1 Contributions of this study

Existing studies that use deep learning models to predict Bitcoin prices, or those predicting other financial products, rarely disclose their code or provide detailed explanations of the specific steps involved in training their deep learning models. However, training deep learning models involves numerous adjustable parameters, such as the number of features, methods for hyperparameter tuning, and the specific architecture of the model. As a result, it is challenging to fully understand how these studies were designed and executed. Furthermore, even when some studies do mention certain aspects of their model setup, they often do not explain the reasoning or logic behind their choices, such as why a certain number of units were set for a layer. This makes it difficult for future research to gain useful and transferable insights from these studies. Additionally, different studies often adopt vastly different approaches, so even though many use the same evaluation metrics such as RMSE and MAPE, the differences in datasets, model complexity, and other factors make cross-study comparisons difficult. Sometimes, even within the same study, researchers use different settings for different models, such as varying the number of layers or units, which can undermine the credibility of their conclusions about the superiority of one model over another.

This paper aims to conduct research using a relatively standardized and streamlined approach, with a focus on minimizing human intervention and decision-making through the use of automated tools. This approach not only allows for a more thorough exploration of the potential of deep learning models and their associated tools but also ensures that the approach used in this research can be easily applied to future studies of interest. Moreover, by using the same inputs and settings across different models, the comparative results between models in this study should be more convincing.

Overall, this study utilized a comprehensive approach, combining hyperparameter tuning, cross-validation, performance metrics testing, volatility analysis, and comparisons both between different models and within the same model class. This approach leveraged the strengths of each method while effectively mitigating their

drawbacks, thus providing a thorough exploration of the overall performance of various deep learning models. For example, using cross-validation and calculating the average validation loss helps provide a more reliable performance estimate by training and validating across multiple data subsets. It aids in detecting overfitting, selecting the best model, and assessing model stability. However, it also has some drawbacks, such as high computational cost and the potential to mask anomalies in specific folds. Moreover, even if the average validation loss is low, it does not guarantee consistent performance in practical applications. For instance, in this study, the models created using the optimal hyperparameters for GRU and GRU-LSTM showed significant volatility in subsequent research. Therefore, it is crucial to combine various research steps and evaluation metrics to gain a comprehensive understanding of the model's actual performance.

9.2 Limitations of this study

First is the limitation of the data. The historical Bitcoin prices and trading volumes used in this study were sourced from Binance, where Bitcoin-related data is only available starting from August 17, 2017. Additionally, the calculation of indicators like the SMA 100 further restricted the dataset size. A larger dataset should be able to improve the training of deep learning models and result in better performance.

The hardware and software configuration for this study was quite basic. The experimental hardware and software environment for training the deep learning models was Google Colaboratory, using a Python 3 Google Compute Engine backend with a CPU and 12.7 GB of RAM. This somewhat limited the training of the deep learning models. For instance, the reason that the number of tuning iterations was set to 80 was that the available RAM could not support more calculations. Performing more hyperparameter tuning trials might have yielded better hyperparameter combinations, potentially resulting in models with enhanced performance. However, the fact that effective models were trained even with such a basic hardware and software environment demonstrates the power of deep learning models and the practicality of applying them to financial time series problems. Additionally, this study only focused on the best hyperparameter combination of each model. The other hyperparameter

combinations, such as the top 5 best hyperparameter combinations of each model, which can be found in appendices, may also be valuable to take a look.

This study only explored the performance of different models under specific input conditions, namely a total of 16 features across 2,442 observations, with 1,950 used for training and 492 for testing. Adjusting the inputs could potentially improve model performance, such as using only Bitcoin's historical data, or including only historical data and technical indicators, or incorporating additional features.

There are also various methods for hybridizing LSTM and GRU models. For example, the hybrid model developed by Girsang (2023) consisted of two parts. The first part included an LSTM layer with 30 units, followed by a Dropout layer, another LSTM layer with 50 units, and then a Dense layer. The second part included a GRU layer with 30 units, followed by a Dropout layer and a Dense layer. The Dense layers from these two parts were connected to a final Dense layer, which generated the output. Therefore, there is potential for further exploration in adjusting hybrid models.

10. Suggestions for future research

Many research directions would be promising, for example:

Firstly, as Bitcoin has grown, many alternative cryptocurrencies (altcoins) have also emerged and developed. Although the cryptocurrency industry is highly volatile, several cryptocurrencies besides Bitcoin, such as ETH, BNB and SOL, have achieved significant market capitalization and widespread market recognition. Therefore, applying machine learning and deep learning models to research altcoins holds great potential. In fact, academic research has already no more only concentrated on Bitcoin (Brauneis and Mestel, 2018). The following are some studies conducted on cryptocurrencies beyond Bitcoin.

Shen et al. (2020) introduced a three-factor pricing model for analyzing over 1700 cryptocurrencies, which included market, size, and reversal factors. They found that smaller cryptocurrencies generally yielded higher returns, with particularly strong reversal effects. Moreover, the three-factor model significantly outperformed the conventional cryptocurrency-CAPM model, showcasing robust performance across

various factor configurations. However, according to Jia et al. (2022) and Liu et al. (2022), the momentum effect rather than the reversal effect should be more accurate, suggesting that the market-size-momentum (MSM) three-factor model would have greater explanatory power. Liu and Tsyvinski (2021) used the number of wallet users, the number of active addresses, the number of transaction counts and the number of payment counts as proxies for the network effect, and electricity costs and computing costs as proxies for the production effect, and concluded that cryptocurrency returns were highly responsive to network factors but not to production factors. Cryptocurrency returns could be forecasted by momentum and investor attention, which, unlike in the stock market, were distinct phenomena with limited interaction. Additionally, cryptocurrency returns had low exposure to traditional asset classes and macroeconomic factors.

There are also some studies utilizing machine learning and deep learning models for cryptocurrency price prediction. For example, Alonso-Monsalve (2020) used MLP, Radial Basis Function Neural Networks (RBFN), CNN and a hybrid CNN-LSTM network to predict whether Bitcoin, Dash, Ethereum, Litecoin, Monero and Ripple would appreciate relative to the USD in the next minute. Their study results indicated that the hybrid CNN-LSTM model significantly outperformed the other models. Patel et al. (2020) proposed a hybrid model based on LSTM and GRU to predict the prices of Litecoin and Monero. The results showed that this hybrid model outperformed using LSTM alone. Girsang (2023) also developed a hybrid LSTM-GRU model to predict the prices of Ethereum and Solana. This method used the historical price data and social media sentiment as inputs for the prediction model. The experimental results showed that the hybrid model successfully predicted the price trends of Ethereum and Solana, and its performance surpassed single LSTM and GRU models. More research on using deep learning models to predict different cryptocurrencies is expected.

Secondly, exploring the performance of other deep learning models, such as CNNs and Transformers, could be valuable. Many studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of CNNs in time series analysis and their widespread use in predicting the returns of financial products like Bitcoin. Specifically, combining CNNs with LSTMs or GRUs,

where CNNs handle pattern recognition and LSTMs or GRUs manage time series processing, has been reported to achieve excellent performance. Therefore, future research could further investigate how CNN architectures can be effectively integrated into the price prediction of Bitcoin and other financial products. The Transformer is a very new model that has not yet been widely studied, making it a highly promising research direction. The Transformer, proposed by Vaswani et al. in 2017, eliminates recurrence and convolution and relies entirely on attention mechanisms. Their experiments on two machine translation tasks demonstrated that Transformer models outperformed existing advanced models, offered greater parallelism and significantly reduced training costs. Few studies have begun exploring the use of Transformers for cryptocurrency price predictions. More research on applying Transformers and hybrid models incorporating Transformers to predict prices of cryptocurrencies and other financial products is foreseeable.

Thirdly, there are many deep learning tools that can be explored for their potential. For instance, aside from Optuna, the hyperparameter tuning tool used in this study, there are many other tools available for Bayesian optimization. Additionally, grid search and random search can also be tried based on research needs. In terms of optimizers, besides Adam and RMSprop, alternatives such as AdamW and Nadam can also be considered. Furthermore, adjusting the tuning space for hyperparameter combinations may lead to improved model performance.

Reference

- Aggarwal, A., Gupta, I., Garg, N., & Goel, A. (2019). Deep learning approach to determine the impact of socioeconomic factors on bitcoin price prediction. In 2019 twelfth international conference on contemporary computing (IC3) (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
- Ali, F., Suryakant, R., & Nimbore, S. (2023). Ensemble Model Based on Deep Learning for Forecasting Crypto Asset Futures in Markets. In 2023 3rd International Conference on Smart Generation Computing, Communication and Networking (SMART GENCON) (pp. 1-8). IEEE.
- Alonso-Monsalve, S., Suárez-Cetrulo, A. L., Cervantes, A., & Quintana, D. (2020). Convolution on neural networks for high-frequency trend prediction of cryptocurrency exchange rates using technical indicators. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 149, 113250.
- Awoke, T., Rout, M., Mohanty, L., & Satapathy, S. C. (2020). Bitcoin price prediction and analysis using deep learning models. In *Communication Software and Networks: Proceedings of INDIA 2019* (pp. 631-640). Singapore: Springer Singapore.
- Balcilar, M., Bouri, E., Gupta, R. & Roubaud, D. (2017). Can volume predict Bitcoin returns and volatility? A quantiles-based approach. *Economic Modelling* 64, 74-81.
- Baur, D.G., Hong, K., Lee, A.D. (2018). Bitcoin: Medium of exchange or speculative assets? *Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions and Money* 54, 177–189.
- Bouoiyour, J. & Selmi, R. (2015). What Does Bitcoin Look Like? *Annals of Economics and Finance* 16-2, 449-492.
- Brauneis, A., Mestel, R. (2018). Price discovery of cryptocurrencies: Bitcoin and beyond. *Economics Letters* 165, 58–61.
- Cho, K., Van Merriënboer, B., Gulcehre, C., Bahdanau, D., Bougares, F., Schwenk, H. and Bengio, Y. (2014). Learning phrase representations using RNN encoder-decoder for statistical machine translation. arXiv:1406.1078v3.
- Ciaian, P., Rajcaniova, M., & Kancs, D. A. (2016). The economics of BitCoin price formation. *Applied economics*, 48(19), 1799-1815.
- Colianni, S., Rosales, S., & Signorotti, M. (2015). Algorithmic trading of cryptocurrency based on Twitter sentiment analysis. *CS229 Project*, 1(5), 1-4.

- Corbet, S., Lucey, B., Peat, M., Vigne, S. (2018). Bitcoin Futures—What use are they? *Economics Letters* 172, 23–27.
- Di Persio, L., & Honchar, O. (2016). Artificial neural networks architectures for stock price prediction: Comparisons and applications. *International journal of circuits, systems and signal processing* 10, 403-413.
- Dixon, C. (2024). *Read write own: building the next era of the internet*. First edition. New York: Random House.
- Donaldson, G. & Kamstra, M. (1997). An artificial neural network-GARCH model for international stock return volatility. *Journal of Empirical Finance*, 4 (1), 17–46.
- Dutta, A., Kumar, S., & Basu, M. (2020). A gated recurrent unit approach to bitcoin price prediction. *Journal of risk and financial management*, 13(2), 23.
- Dyhrberg, A. H. (2016). Bitcoin, gold and the dollar - A GARCH volatility analysis. *Finance Research Letters* 16, 85-92.
- Ekman, M. (2022). *Learning deep learning. Theory and practice of neural networks, computer vision, natural language processing, and transformers using TensorFlow*. NVIDIA Corporation.
- Garcia D., Tessone C., Mavrodiev P. & Perony N. (2014). The digital traces of bubbles: feedback cycles between socio-economic signals in the Bitcoin economy. *Journal of the Royal Society Interface*, 11: 20140623.
- Georgoula, I., Pournarakis, D., Bilanakos, C., Sotiropoulos, D., Sotiropoulos, D. & Giaglis, G. (2015). Using time-series and sentiment analysis to detect the determinants of Bitcoin prices. Available at SSRN 2607167.
- Gers, F. A., Schmidhuber, J. & Cummins, F. (2000). Learning to forget: Continual prediction with LSTM. *Neural computation*, 12(10), 2451-2471.
- Girsang, A. S. (2023). Hybrid LSTM and GRU for cryptocurrency price forecasting based on social network sentiment analysis using FinBERT. *IEEE Access*, 11, 120530-120540.
- Goodfellow, I., Bengio, Y. & Courville, A. (2017). *Deep learning*. Cambridge, MA, USA: MIT press.
- Greaves, A., & Au, B. (2015). Using the bitcoin transaction graph to predict the price

of bitcoin. *No data*, 8, 416-443.

Guo, Q., Lei, S., Ye, Q., Fang, Z. (2021). MRC-LSTM: A hybrid approach of Multi-scale Residual CNN and LSTM to predict Bitcoin price. *arXiv:2105.00707v1*.

Hochreiter, S. & Schmidhuber, J. (1997). Long short-term memory. *Neural Computation*, 9 (8), 1735-1780.

Huang, W., Nakamori, Y. & Wang, S. (2005). Forecasting stock market movement direction with support vector machine. *Computers & Operations Research* 32(10), 2513-2522.

Islam, M.S. & Hossain, E. (2021). Foreign exchange currency rate prediction using a GRU-LSTM hybrid network. *Soft Computing Letters* 3, 100009.

Jang, H., & Lee, J. (2018). An empirical study on modeling and prediction of Bitcoin prices with Bayesian Neural Networks based on Blockchain information. *IEEE Access* 6, 5427-5437.

Jay, P., Kalariya, V., Parmar, P., Tanwar, S., Kumar, N. & Alazab, M. (2020). Stochastic neural networks for cryptocurrency price prediction. *IEEE Access* 8, 82804-82818.

Ji, S., Kim, J., & Im, H. (2019). A comparative study of bitcoin price prediction using deep learning. *Mathematics*, 7(10), 898.

Jia, B., Goodell, J.W. & Shen, D. (2022). Momentum or reversal: Which is the appropriate third factor for cryptocurrencies? *Finance Research Letters* 45, 102139.

Kervanci, I. S., Akay, M. F., & Özceylan, E. (2023). Bitcoin price prediction using LSTM, GRU and hybrid LSTM-GRU with bayesian optimization, random search, and grid search for the next days. *Journal of Industrial and Management Optimization*.

Kim, H.Y. & Won, C.H. (2018). Forecasting the volatility of stock price index: A hybrid model integrating LSTM with multiple GARCH-type models. *Expert Systems with Applications* 103, 25-37.

Kristoufek, L. (2013). Bitcoin meets Google Trends and Wikipedia: Quantifying the relationship between phenomena of the Internet era. *Scientific Reports* 3: 1-7.

Kristoufek, L. (2015). What are the main drivers of the Bitcoin price? Evidence from wavelet coherence analysis. *PLoS One* 10 (4), e0123923.

Kumar, M.R., Umar, S., Venkatram, V. (2023). Short term memory recurrent neural

network-based machine learning model for predicting Bit-coin market prices. *Grenze International Journal of Engineering and Technology*, Jan Issue, 1683-1689.

Ladhari, A., & Boubaker, H. (2024). Deep Learning Models for Bitcoin Prediction Using Hybrid Approaches with Gradient-Specific Optimization. *Forecasting* 6, 279-295.

Lauretto, M. S., Silva, B. B., & Andrade, P. M. (2013). Evaluation of a supervised learning approach for stock market operations. arXiv preprint arXiv:1301.4944.

Li, Y., & Dai, W. (2020). Bitcoin price forecasting method based on CNN-LSTM hybrid neural network model. *The Journal of Engineering* 13, 344-347.

Liu, Y. & Tsyvinski, A. (2021). Risks and returns of cryptocurrency. *The Review of Financial Studies* 34 (6), 2689-2727.

Liu, Y., Tsyvinski, A. & Wu, X. (2022). Common risk factors in cryptocurrency. *The Journal of Finance*, 77 (2), 1133-1177.

Livieris, L.E., Pintelas, E. & Pintelas, P. (2020). A CNN–LSTM model for gold price time-series forecasting. *Neural Computing and Applications* 32, 17351–17360.

Madan, I., Saluja, S., & Zhao, A. (2015). Automated bitcoin trading via machine learning algorithms. URL: [http://cs229.stanford.edu/proj2014/Isaac% 20Madan](http://cs229.stanford.edu/proj2014/Isaac%20Madan), 20.

Mahfooz, A., & Phillips, J.L. (2024). Conditional forecasting of Bitcoin prices using exogenous variables. *IEEE Access* 12, 44510–44526.

Maknickienė, N. & Maknickas, A. (2012). Application of neural network for forecasting of exchange rates and forex trading. *The 7th International Scientific Conference, Business and Management*, 122-127.

Matta, M., Lunesu, I., & Marchesi, M. (2015). Bitcoin spread prediction using social and web search media. *Proceedings of DeCAT*.

McNally, S., Roche, J., & Caton, S. (2018). Predicting the price of Bitcoin using machine learning. *26th Euromicro International Conference on Parallel, Distributed and Network-based Processing (PDP)*. IEEE, 339–343.

Nakamoto, S. (2008). Bitcoin: A peer-to-peer electronic cash system.

Nelson, D. M., Pereira, A. C. & De Oliveira, R. A. (2017). Stock market's price movement prediction with LSTM neural networks. *2017 International joint conference*

- on neural networks (IJCNN), IEEE, 1419-1426.
- Patel, M. M., Tanwar, S., Gupta, R., & Kumar, N. (2020). A deep learning-based cryptocurrency price prediction scheme for financial institutions. *Journal of information security and applications*, 55, 102583.
- Rahman, S., Hemel, J. N., Anta, S. J. A., Al Muhee, H., & Uddin, J. (2018). Sentiment analysis using R: An approach to correlate cryptocurrency price fluctuations with change in user sentiment using machine learning. In 2018 Joint 7th International Conference on Informatics, Electronics & Vision (ICIEV) and 2018 2nd International Conference on Imaging, Vision & Pattern Recognition (icIVPR) (pp. 492-497). IEEE.
- Sandner, P., Tumasjan, A., Welp, I. (2019). *Der Blockchain Faktor: Wie die Blockchain unsere Gesellschaft verändern wird*. Norderstedt: BoD – Books on Demand
- Sharang, A. & Rao, C. (2015). Using machine learning for medium frequency derivative portfolio trading. arXiv:1512.06228.
- Shen, D., Urquhart, A. & Wang, P. (2020). A three-factor pricing model for cryptocurrencies. *Finance Research Letters* 34, 101248.
- Tanwar, S., Patel, N. P., Patel, S. N., Patel, J. R., Sharma, G. & Davidson, I. E. (2021). Deep learning-based cryptocurrency price prediction scheme with interdependent relations. *IEEE Access* 9, 138633-138646.
- Vassiliadis, S., Papadopoulos, P., Rangoussi, M., Konieczny, T., Gralowski, J. (2017). Bitcoin value analysis based on cross-correlations. *Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce* 22, S7.
- Vaswani, A., Shazeer, N., Parmar, N., Uszkoreit, J., Jones, L., Gomez, A.N., Kaiser, L., & Polosukhin, I. (2017). Attention is all you need. 31st Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems (NIPS), Long Beach, CA, USA.
- Velde, F. (2013). Bitcoin: A Primer. Chicago Fed Letter. Essays on Issues, number 317. The Federal Reserve Bank of Chicago.
- Wang, Y., & Choi, I. C. (2013). Market index and stock price direction prediction using machine learning techniques: an empirical study on the KOSPI and HSI. arXiv preprint arXiv:1309.7119, 1-13.
- Wang, P., Li, X., Shen, D. & Zhang, W. (2020). How does economic policy uncertainty

affect the bitcoin market? *Research in International Business and Finance* 53, 101234.

Wang, C., Shen, D. & Li, Y. (2022). Aggregate investor attention and Bitcoin return: The long short-term memory networks perspective. *Finance Research Letters* 49, 103143.

Yermack, D. (2015). Is Bitcoin a real currency? An economic appraisal. *Handbook of Digital Currency* 31-43.

Zhang, Y., Chu, G., Shen, D. (2021). The role of investor attention in predicting stock prices: The long short-term memory networks perspective. *Finance Research Letters* 38, 101484.

Appendices

Appendix 1. Top 5 trials of LSTM hyperparameter optimization

Trial 1: Value: 0.17125244965427555. Parameters: {'timesteps': 20, 'batch_size': 16, 'units_layer1': 50, 'dropout_rate_layer1': 0.1, 'units_layer2': 40, 'dropout_rate_layer2': 0.1, 'optimizer': 'adam', 'learning_rate': 0.001063189574959334}

Trial 2: Value: 0.1722134158073459. Parameters: {'timesteps': 20, 'batch_size': 16, 'units_layer1': 50, 'dropout_rate_layer1': 0.1, 'units_layer2': 40, 'dropout_rate_layer2': 0.1, 'optimizer': 'adam', 'learning_rate': 0.0050125801997217105}

Trial 3: Value: 0.17543497908045538. Parameters: {'timesteps': 20, 'batch_size': 32, 'units_layer1': 30, 'dropout_rate_layer1': 0.1, 'units_layer2': 40, 'dropout_rate_layer2': 0.1, 'optimizer': 'adam', 'learning_rate': 0.0019624920724733786}

Trial 4: Value: 0.17639488659333438. Parameters: {'timesteps': 20, 'batch_size': 16, 'units_layer1': 50, 'dropout_rate_layer1': 0.1, 'units_layer2': 50, 'dropout_rate_layer2': 0.1, 'optimizer': 'adam', 'learning_rate': 0.0060930286286496015}

Trial 5: Value: 0.18060312286834232. Parameters: {'timesteps': 20, 'batch_size': 16, 'units_layer1': 70, 'dropout_rate_layer1': 0.1, 'units_layer2': 40, 'dropout_rate_layer2': 0.1, 'optimizer': 'adam', 'learning_rate': 0.0039721704397292935}

Appendix 2. Top 5 trials of GRU hyperparameter optimization

Trial 1: Value: 0.03766969048883766. Parameters: {'timesteps': 10, 'batch_size': 16, 'units_layer1': 70, 'dropout_rate_layer1': 0.2, 'units_layer2': 40, 'dropout_rate_layer2': 0.4, 'optimizer': 'rmsprop', 'learning_rate': 0.0009474097135596231}

Trial 2: Value: 0.041023187525570395. Parameters: {'timesteps': 10, 'batch_size': 16, 'units_layer1': 70, 'dropout_rate_layer1': 0.2, 'units_layer2': 40, 'dropout_rate_layer2': 0.30000000000000004, 'optimizer': 'rmsprop', 'learning_rate': 0.0011486073496005567}

Trial 3: Value: 0.0460254933568649. Parameters: {'timesteps': 10, 'batch_size': 16, 'units_layer1': 70, 'dropout_rate_layer1': 0.2, 'units_layer2': 40, 'dropout_rate_layer2': 0.4, 'optimizer': 'rmsprop', 'learning_rate': 0.0007855271490256491}

Trial 4: Value: 0.047689415520289914. Parameters: {'timesteps': 10, 'batch_size': 32,

'units_layer1': 60, 'dropout_rate_layer1': 0.4, 'units_layer2': 40, 'dropout_rate_layer2': 0.2, 'optimizer': 'rmsprop', 'learning_rate': 0.001647016384757289}

Trial 5: Value: 0.04794295983738266. Parameters: {'timesteps': 10, 'batch_size': 16, 'units_layer1': 60, 'dropout_rate_layer1': 0.2, 'units_layer2': 40, 'dropout_rate_layer2': 0.4, 'optimizer': 'rmsprop', 'learning_rate': 0.0009319740884202844}

Appendix 3. Top 5 trials of LSTM-GRU hyperparameter optimization

Trial 1: Value: 0.12843572478159332. Parameters: {'timesteps': 50, 'batch_size': 16, 'units_layer1': 50, 'dropout_rate_layer1': 0.4, 'units_layer2': 50, 'dropout_rate_layer2': 0.4, 'optimizer': 'adam', 'learning_rate': 0.0017249472838219754}

Trial 2: Value: 0.1367211099015549. Parameters: {'timesteps': 50, 'batch_size': 16, 'units_layer1': 60, 'dropout_rate_layer1': 0.4, 'units_layer2': 50, 'dropout_rate_layer2': 0.4, 'optimizer': 'adam', 'learning_rate': 0.0030894474428621215}

Trial 3: Value: 0.13704690685262905. Parameters: {'timesteps': 50, 'batch_size': 16, 'units_layer1': 30, 'dropout_rate_layer1': 0.4, 'units_layer2': 50, 'dropout_rate_layer2': 0.4, 'optimizer': 'adam', 'learning_rate': 0.0034770105151008296}

Trial 4: Value: 0.15230896107968875. Parameters: {'timesteps': 50, 'batch_size': 16, 'units_layer1': 60, 'dropout_rate_layer1': 0.4, 'units_layer2': 50, 'dropout_rate_layer2': 0.4, 'optimizer': 'adam', 'learning_rate': 0.004249095615482288}

Trial 5: Value: 0.1558786847977899. Parameters: {'timesteps': 50, 'batch_size': 16, 'units_layer1': 60, 'dropout_rate_layer1': 0.4, 'units_layer2': 50, 'dropout_rate_layer2': 0.4, 'optimizer': 'adam', 'learning_rate': 0.0021137268616813333}

Appendix 4. Top 5 trials of GRU-LSTM hyperparameter optimization

Trial 1: Value: 0.1975953074754216. Parameters: {'timesteps': 20, 'batch_size': 64, 'units_layer1': 60, 'dropout_rate_layer1': 0.30000000000000004, 'units_layer2': 40, 'dropout_rate_layer2': 0.2, 'optimizer': 'rmsprop', 'learning_rate': 0.0006224805845129522}

Trial 2: Value: 0.23798508163308724. Parameters: {'timesteps': 50, 'batch_size': 32, 'units_layer1': 50, 'dropout_rate_layer1': 0.1, 'units_layer2': 50, 'dropout_rate_layer2':

0.1, 'optimizer': 'rmsprop', 'learning_rate': 0.00013373380511716844}

Trial 3: Value: 0.24586830622283742. Parameters: {'timesteps': 10, 'batch_size': 48, 'units_layer1': 70, 'dropout_rate_layer1': 0.30000000000000004, 'units_layer2': 40, 'dropout_rate_layer2': 0.2, 'optimizer': 'rmsprop', 'learning_rate': 0.0004538769525155324}

Trial 4: Value: 0.24979322096332907. Parameters: {'timesteps': 10, 'batch_size': 64, 'units_layer1': 60, 'dropout_rate_layer1': 0.30000000000000004, 'units_layer2': 40, 'dropout_rate_layer2': 0.2, 'optimizer': 'rmsprop', 'learning_rate': 0.0015107089573456077}

Trial 5: Value: 0.2528118966612965. Parameters: {'timesteps': 100, 'batch_size': 48, 'units_layer1': 40, 'dropout_rate_layer1': 0.30000000000000004, 'units_layer2': 50, 'dropout_rate_layer2': 0.2, 'optimizer': 'rmsprop', 'learning_rate': 8.454575310178709e-05}